

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

UTILIZING JOINT COMMISSION PERINATAL STANDARDS: A NURSE EDUCATION
PROGRAM FOR POSTPARTUM HYPERTENSION AND PREECLAMPSIA

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Beleda Saziru

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Manal Alatrash, PhD, RN, Team Leader
Laura Sarff, DNP, RN, MBA, CPHQ, NEA-BC, Team Member

July 2021

Author Note

Beleda Saziru - <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7657-7429>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4796304

© 2021 Beleda Saziru

ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of this QI project was to develop, implement and evaluate a nurse education program. This program was used to develop an education protocol that followed the new Joint Commission (JC) perinatal standard requirement. The objective was to reduce morbidity and mortality caused by postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia using the guide of the new JC perinatal standard. This project aimed to examine changes in nurses' clinical understanding of the disease state and evaluated their self-efficacy in the usage of evidence-based practices. A final objective was to assess readmission rates before and after implementing the educational intervention. **Background:** Recently, the JC issued two new perinatal standards that were mandated to start on January 1, 2021. The first standard focused on maternal hemorrhage, whereas the second one addressed postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. Postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia contribute to a significant number of obstetrical readmissions. **Methodology:** This project employed a single-group pretest-posttest (nurse-nurses) design. Postpartum nurses were recruited to receive the nurse educational program of the project regarding postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. The single nurse group design involved nurse participants who received an intervention. This nursing group was evaluated before and after the educational program. Data collection was conducted using the project survey at baseline and after program completion. The project survey included the Postpartum Nursing Knowledge and Teaching Survey and the Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self-Efficacy scale. Data was collected on the nurse-provided postpartum education during maternal admission and from birth to discharge from the hospital. **Results:** Demographics represented the nurse population. **Discussion:** Educational intervention increased nurses' knowledge and self-efficacy and readmissions. Recommendations for practice change addressed nurse education related to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia.

Keywords: postpartum hypertension, postpartum preeclampsia postpartum readmissions

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	iv
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	5
Element Three.....	8
Element Six.....	9
Purpose Statement.....	11
Framework	12
The Iowa Model.....	12
Steps of the Iowa Model	13
Application of Iowa Model to Current Project	17
Use of Iowa Model in Research and Practice	19
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	24
Risk Factors of Postpartum Hypertension and Preeclampsia	25
Readmission Due to Postpartum Readmission	27
Factors Associated with Postpartum Readmission	30
Nursing Education	33
Joint Commission Perinatal Standard and Related Education	40
Patient Perceptions toward Education and Readiness to Learn	43
Appraisal of the Literature Review	45
Conclusion	47
METHODS	48
Design	48
Setting	49
Participants.....	50
Ethical Consideration.....	50
Data Collection	51
Postpartum Nursing Knowledge and Teaching Survey	51
Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self-Efficacy Scale.....	52
Procedure	54
Educational Intervention.....	55

Timeline of the QI Project	56
Data Analysis	56
Types of Control Charts.....	58
Evaluation Plan	59
Conclusion	60
RESULTS	61
Population and Facility Demographic Characteristics.....	61
Postpartum Knowledge Teaching Survey.....	63
Evidence-Based Self Efficacy Scale.....	76
Readmission Rates	77
Conclusion	79
DISCUSSION.....	80
Sociodemographic Data.....	80
Postpartum Knowledge.....	80
Self-Efficacy	81
Readmission Rates	82
Strengths and Limitations	83
Future Clinical Implications	84
Conclusion	85
REFERENCES	86
APPENDIX A: Approval Notice.....	103
APPENDIX B: Postpartum Knowledge and Teaching Survey	105
APPENDIX C: Self-Efficacy Scale.....	112
APPENDIX D: Educational Pamphlet.....	114
APPENDIX E: Permission Letter.....	115
APPENDIX F: Research Study Consent Form.....	116
APPENDIX G: Permission to Use Self Efficacy Scale	119
APPENDIX H: Permission to use Postpartum Nursing Knowledge Teaching Survey.....	120
APPENDIX I: Permission to use Postpartum Preeclampsia Pamphlet	121
APPENDIX J: Recruitment Flyer.....	122

APPENDIX K: IRB Approval123

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Evaluation and Measurement of Outcomes	57
2. Sample Demographics	63
3. Faculty Demographics	64

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care.....	16
2. Question 10: Pre and Post Nurse Awareness of the Number of Deaths Each Year .	65
3. Question 11: Pre and Post Nurse Awareness of the Percentage of Maternal Deaths	65
4. Question 12: Pre and Post Awareness of Top Three Causes of Maternal Mortality .	66
5. Question 13: Pre and Post Nurse Awareness of Maternal Morbidity	67
6. Question 14: Pre and Post Assessment of Day Postpartum Education is Provided...	68
7. Day of Discharge: Pre and Post Time Spent Reinforcing Discharge Information	68
8. Pre and Post Assessment of Belief that Nurses are Responsible for Educating Women	69
9. Nurses' Time Spent Teaching About Warning Signs for Potential Complications...	70
10. Likelihood of Discussing Complications with Women	71
11. Likelihood of Discussing Signs and Symptoms of Complications with Women	72
12. Feelings of Competence Discussing Postpartum Topics with Women	73
13. Helpfulness of a One Page Educational Handout of Warning Signs.....	73
14. Documentation of Postpartum Education	74
15. Use of Resources to Increase Knowledge Regarding Postpartum Mortality and Morbidity	75
16. Methods Identified by Participants for Staying Up to Date on Evidenced-Based Practices	75
17. Awareness of the Relationship between Mortality, Morbidity, and Postpartum Education	76
18. Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self-Efficacy Scale: A Measure of Confidence ..	77
19. T-Chart.....	78

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to first thank God for getting me through this rigorous DNP program. I would like to thank my mom for her love, encouragement, and support throughout the program. I would like to thank my exceptional team Dr. Manal Alatrash and Dr. Laura Sarff for their support and expertise. I am truly blessed to have such a phenomenal team. I also want to express my sincere appreciation to Tanisha Dickens and Ronda Sawyer for allowing me to conduct my project at their facility. I would like to also thank my sister Dr. Tiriza Saziru for her love and support. I would like to acknowledge Dr. Andrea Curry for always providing a listening ear when I was in distress. I would also like to thank my prayer warriors, Prophetess Ineal Poole and Taminka Fowler. Lastly, I would like to dedicate this project to my father the late great Dr. Nathan K. Saziru Sr. “Daddy, I followed in your footsteps, and I hope you are very proud of me.”

Background

Pregnancy is the process of carrying a baby for approximately nine months; in most cases, a woman carries a baby for 37 weeks to 42 weeks, which is known as the gestation period (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2020). Pregnancies with complications are on the rise (CDC, 2020). One of the most common complications is hypertension during pregnancy including chronic hypertension, gestational hypertension, preeclampsia super-imposed on chronic hypertension, and preeclampsia (Sutton et al., 2018; Townsend et al., 2016). Women who are pregnant with preexisting hypertension are identified as having chronic hypertension (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists [ACOG], 2020). Women who develop hypertension after 20 weeks of pregnancy have gestational hypertension (ACOG, 2020; Dhariwal & Lynde, 2017). Super-imposed chronic hypertension with preeclampsia is a form of hypertension that takes a sudden exacerbation of hypertension characterized by a sudden elevation in blood pressure (BP), new onset of protein in the urine, and decreased platelet count, thrombocytopenia (ACOG, 2020; Dhariwal & Lynde, 2017). Preeclampsia and eclampsia account for 63,000 deaths annually world (Ross, 2019; Vigil-De Gracia, 2009).

Preeclampsia is a medical condition that occurs at approximately 20 weeks gestational age or greater during pregnancy (Morton et al., 2019; Phillips & Boyd, 2016). Mild preeclampsia is defined as a blood pressure (BP) greater than 140/90 measured twice at least four hours apart (Dhariwal & Lynde, 2017; Phipps et al., 2016). If it is left untreated, a severe form of hypertension may develop, leading to a BP greater than 160/110. Severe preeclampsia is defined as a BP greater than 160/110 measured at two different time periods, separated by at least four hours (Bernstein et al., 2017; Sharma & Kilpatrick, 2017). A patient with severe preeclampsia will exhibit features such as a headache, blurred vision, epigastric pain, and proteinuria, which is

an abnormally excessive amount of protein in the urine (Dhariwal & Lynde, 2017). Preeclamptic patients also exhibit edema, excessive fluid retention in the body leading to body swelling (El-Sayed, 2017; Townsend et al., 2016). Thrombocytopenia and abnormal liver function tests sometimes accompany preeclampsia (El-Sayed, 2017).

It is often necessary to address a wide range of acute care issues with pregnant women, such as those issues related to high BP during and after birth that arise in pregnancy. Approximately 14% of pregnancies are affected by preeclampsia worldwide (WHO, 2018). Approximately five to 8% of pregnancies in the United States involve preeclampsia (CDC, 2020), which accounts for approximately 17% of deaths in California; it is ranked one of the top six causes of maternal mortality in the US (California Department of Public Health [CDPH], 2018; Peneva et al., 2016). Severe preeclampsia can escalate to eclampsia. If left untreated, eclampsia can be life threatening, lead to seizures, stroke, liver failure, pulmonary edema, heart failure, brain damage, or possibly death (Sutton et al., 2018; Vilchez et al., 2016). It can also cause multi organ damage and liver damage. Some women who develop eclampsia may also develop hemolysis, elevated liver enzyme levels, and low platelets known as HELLP syndrome (Morton et al., 2019; Sutton et al., 2018). Patients with HELLP syndrome may bleed to death due to a lack of blood clotting factors with liver failure (Combs, 2017; Morton et al., 2019). This syndrome can significantly affect one's ability to perform activities of daily living such as bathing, getting dressed, motor coordination, cooking, reading, and caring for others such as a newborn infant. Swelling and bleeding in the brain may occur from the eclamptic seizures and stroke (Hammer & Cipolla, 2015).

According to the ACOG (2020), preeclampsia has increased by 25% over the last two decades in the United States. The CDC (2020) indicated that preeclampsia occurs in 1 out of

every 25 pregnancies. Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy including preeclampsia are an increasing cause of severe morbidity, long term disability, and death among both mothers and newborns (Hammer & Cipolla, 2015; World Health Organization [WHO], 2018). Women with a history of preeclampsia or nephritis, with or without a history of hypertension are at risk. Other risk factors for preeclampsia include chronic hypertension, diabetes mellitus, multiple gestation, pre-pregnancy body mass index (BMI) over 30 kg/m, autoimmune diseases, such as lupus, in-vitro fertilization, chronic kidney disease, women over 35, and a family history of preeclampsia, with or without a history of hypertension (ACOG, 2020; Hao et al., 2019; Wagner et al., 2019).

Preeclampsia does not have primary prevention including measures aiming at avoiding the development of the disease among healthy individuals (ACOG, 2020; Matei et al., 2019; Sutton et al., 2018). However, some studies found that using daily low dose aspirin had positive results in preventing morbidities due to preeclampsia and therefore, aspirin was recommended for this purpose (Gu et al., 2020; Sutton et al., 2018; WHO, 2018). According to the United States Preventive Services Task Force, patients should begin a low daily dose of aspirin after 12 weeks of pregnancy and stop at 36 weeks of pregnancy if they have certain risk factors (WHO, 2018; LeFevre, 2014). Thus, postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia has secondary prevention that focuses on prevention of morbidities caused by the disease and early detection of the disease. The ACOG (2020) emphasized the importance of addressing risk factors of preeclampsia and measures necessary to reduce the woman's risk, such as reducing weight and controlling chronic hypertension before getting pregnant. Preeclampsia may rapidly progress to eclampsia, a medical emergency; therefore, weight, edema, and BP must studiously be monitored in these patients (ACOG, 2020). Medications, such as hydralazine or labetalol, for hypertension control and magnesium sulfate for seizure prevention are standard preeclampsia treatment (El-

Sayed, 2017; Sharma, & Kilpatrick, 2017). The cure for preeclampsia is the delivery of the fetus; when elevated BP occurs after a woman has given birth, it is referred to as postpartum hypertension (Sharma & Kilpatrick, 2017).

Postpartum hypertension may occur soon after birth regardless of the patient's history of high BP (Goel et al., 2015; Powles & Gandhi, 2017). It is a form of hypertensive disease that can occur immediately from the time of birth up till twelve weeks (Katsi et al., 2020; Powles & Gandhi, 2017). Patients experiencing postpartum hypertension present with headaches, dizziness, and irritability (Suplee et al., 2016b). Preeclampsia during pregnancy is one of the causes of postpartum hypertension/postpartum preeclampsia (ACOG, 2020; Katsi et al., 2020). Other potential causes of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia are the extra use of intravenous fluids during labor and delivery and the use of nonsteroidal medications in postpartum (ACOG, 2020; Katsi et al., 2020). In postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, the patient experiences a rapid onset of high BP that can occur up till twelve weeks post-delivery (Katsi et al., 2020). This is called late or delayed-onset postpartum preeclampsia, which is defined as the initial diagnosis between 48 hours and six weeks postpartum in patients without previous diagnosis of preeclampsia or any hypertensive disorder (Redman et al., 2019). The prevalence of postpartum hypertensive disorders such as postpartum preeclampsia ranges from .3% - 27.5% (Redman et al., 2019).

Women with a history of preeclampsia, with or without a history of hypertension, are at risk for postpartum/hypertension/ preeclampsia. Other risk factors for postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia include chronic hypertension, diabetes mellitus, multiple gestation, pre-pregnancy BMI over 30kg/m, autoimmune diseases, in-vitro fertilization, chronic kidney disease, women over 35 years of age, chronic kidney disease, and a family history of preeclampsia, with or

without a history of hypertension (Goel et al., 2015; Wen et al., 2019). Like preeclampsia, postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia cannot be prevented and may rapidly progress to eclampsia (Katsi et al., 2020).

Problem Statement

Although postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia cannot be prevented, women's risk to develop these two conditions and their subsequent readmissions can be significantly reduced (Katsi et al., 2020). According to a multistate retrospective cohort study, postpartum readmission rates in the states of California, New York, and Florida went from 1.72% in 2004 and 2.16% in 2011 (Clapp et al., 2016). The most common indications for readmissions were infection ranking first at 15.5%, hypertension ranking second at 9.3%, and mental illness ranking third at 7.7% (Clapp et al., 2016). The average readmission day for postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia was day three of discharge (Clapp et al., 2016).

The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid (CMS, 2020) have attempted to control the cost associated with hospital readmissions by implementing the Hospital Readmission Reduction Program (HRRP). The HRRP program lowers reimbursements to hospitals with a high number of readmissions. Hospital readmissions are expensive and excessive spanning up to 41 billion for patients readmitted within 30 days of discharge (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], n.d.). The Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project analyzed postpartum readmission based on length of stay after delivery. The project found that 1.6% of women were readmitted due to hypertension-related diagnoses with readmission that occurred within 10 days of discharge. Hospital readmissions are expensive; charges increase significantly with the number of days a patient is admitted (Wen et al., 2018). Hospital readmissions can negatively impact patient outcomes and cost. Therefore, acute care settings aim to decrease readmissions and

increase providers' knowledge on how to prevent negative outcomes of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia.

In addition to the CMS, another regulatory body, the Joint Commission (JC), requires the health facility to develop well-written evidence-based procedures to outline the stage-based management of postpartum preeclampsia (JC, 2019; Troiano & Witcher, 2018). A major objective of the JC is to continuously improve and enhance the quality and safety of healthcare delivery in the U.S. It is vital to ensure that members of the healthcare team clearly communicate and work in collaboration with each other to minimize hypertensive risk (JC, 2019). According to the JC (2019), all healthcare providers caring for patients should be provided with specific education about their roles and how to be efficient in assessing, educating, and taking the right measurements.

The JC created two new perinatal standards, which were mandated to start on January 1, 2021 (JC, 2019). The first standard focuses on maternal hemorrhage, whereas the second one addresses hypertension and preeclampsia, which was the focus of this quality improvement (QI) project. The hypertension/preeclampsia standard incorporates six elements of performance (JC, 2019). The elements of performance have been developed by the JC to enhance the quality and safety of care that healthcare professionals provide to females at all stages of gestation and post-delivery (JC, 2019) The new elements of performance are incorporated in the provisions of care, treatment, and services chapter.

The perinatal standard was developed to reduce the likelihood of harm related to maternal hypertension/preeclampsia and includes the following elements: (a) develop written evidence-based procedures for measuring and re-measuring BP. These procedures include criteria that identify patients with severely elevated BP; (b) develop written evidenced-based procedures for

managing pregnant and postpartum patients with severe hypertension/preeclampsia related to emergency response medications, the use of seizure prophylaxis, consulting additional experts, using fetal monitoring and considering emergent delivery; (c) provide role-specific education to all staff and providers who treat pregnant/postpartum patients about the hospital's evidence-based severe hypertension/preeclampsia procedure; (d) conduct drills at least once a year to determine system issues as part of ongoing quality improvement efforts. Severe hypertension/preeclampsia drills include a team debrief; (e) review severe hypertension/preeclampsia cases that meet criteria established by the hospital to evaluate the effectiveness of the care, treatment, and services provided to the patient during the event; and (f) provide printed education to preeclampsia patients, and their families, including the designated support person whenever possible. At a minimum, education should include signs and symptoms of severe hypertension/preeclampsia during hospitalization that alert the patient to seek immediate care and signs and symptoms of severe hypertension/preeclampsia after discharge that alert the patient to seek immediate care and when to schedule discharge follow-up appointments (JC, 2019).

Due to rising maternal mortality throughout the world (CDC, 2020), educational materials for women who are pregnant and who recently delivered are essential (D'Oria et al., 2016). Improving the patient's knowledge will prompt them to identify the onset of signs and symptoms of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia early on which may lead to seeking early medical care and treatment, hence, preventing complications and morbidities related to the disease (Zuckerwise & Lipkind, 2017; Suplee et al., 2016b). Nurses, consequently, are required to provide more effective patient education and reinforcement to this high-risk population (Suplee et al., 2016b). It is imperative to strengthen the teaching and to educate all postpartum

patients to prevent re-hospitalizations, strokes, seizures, financial burden, and mortality that can be caused by the disease.

There is limited published literature on the number of hospitals following the new JC perinatal standards. However, in 2020 Linda Zimmer recruited 150 healthcare clinicians and educators who completed a survey about their organization's readiness to comply with the new perinatal standards (HealthStream, 2021). The respondents included nurse managers, employees in quality improvement and infection control with more than 63% of them who represented acute care hospitals. Readiness for the JC surveyors were found to be low, ranged from 41–78% (HealthStream, 2021). These low scores could be attributed to the current Covid-19 pandemic (Durkee, 2020).

A postpartum unit in an acute care setting in southern California, where this QI project was implemented, has experienced an increase in the number of patients readmitted for postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia (Kaiser Health Connect Epic Computer System, 2020). On this unit, four of the six elements of performance included in the new JC perinatal standard were followed; however, the third and sixth elements of performance were not being followed.

Element Three

To address element three, I provided role-specific education to all staff and providers who treat pregnant/postpartum patients about the hospital's evidence-based severe hypertension/preeclampsia procedure; all the nurses must be offered training on how to utilize the postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia protocol when they are newly hired during orientations. Currently, the newly hired postpartum nurses are not offered this kind of education during their orientation. The unit-specific orientation consists of teaching the new nurses about the routine workflow within the unit, hospital policies, how to document using the Epic computer

charting system, and tasks, procedures and tests related to the postpartum mother and newborn infant (Kaiser Permanente, 2020). During the unit-specific orientation, the new-hire activities consist of the nurse completing a scavenger hunt to learn where supplies and equipment are located on the unit and how to document patient acuties. Often, the new nurse must wait several months to attend a critical event training to educate them about what to do in the event of a postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia emergency. The postpartum unit does not have a standardized nursing education program for new nurses.

Nurses should be educated to be able to effectively assess postpartum patients and educate them about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. According to Suplee et al. (2016b), nurses are the healthcare workers tasked with the responsibility of performing most of the postpartum education for patients; it is vital for nurses to work to enhance discharge education (Suplee et al., 2016b). Such education allows for dissemination of critical information to patients in a well-timed, competent, and evidence-based manner. Nurses provide patients with information on different aspects concerning transitioning to their homes and how to take care of their newborns. During the admission and discharge processes of a patient, the learning needs of those patients must be assessed (Temiz et al., 2016).

Element Six

Despite the new JC perinatal standards that recommend all patients who have given birth are educated about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, nurses on that postpartum unit teach only those patients at high risk for postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia (Kaiser Permanente, 2020). Failure to educate all those women indicates a failure to comply with JC standards, leading to a potential decline in patient care and higher morbidity and mortality rates either in the hospital or post-discharge. Furthermore, complying with the JC standards and regulations is

necessary for the healthcare setting to get accredited. The Joint Commission is a nonprofit organization based in the United States that accredits over 20,000 healthcare organizations and programs in the country (JC, 2019). To enhance patient safety, the JC monitors, and advocates for legislation, which is achieved by collaborating with authorities in charge of patient safety and dealing with state regulations to minimize expectations that seem unrealistic and also reform the outdated rules. The JC also accredits healthcare centers offering office-based, ambulatory, home healthcare, behavioral health, laboratory, and nursing services. According to Wadhwa and Huynh (2020), the award is given to facilities that follow the standards and policies of patient safety strictly. Healthcare facilities accredited by the JC benefit significantly as the community becomes confident in their treatment and services of care. The JC aids healthcare facilities in organizing and strengthening patient safety efforts which ensures that all patients receive quality healthcare.

The postpartum unit of this project needs to fully adhere to the new perinatal standard, especially because this unit lacks an effective and standardized discharge teaching process about addressing postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. The acute care facility of the project does not currently follow the updated JC standardized discharge teaching related to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, resulting in patients being discharged without a solid understanding of their diagnosis, medications, and the need for BP monitoring, lowering sodium intake, and avoiding fatty foods (Yen & Leasure, 2019). Nurses are responsible for providing comprehensive, effective education to patients throughout their hospital stay and at discharge since this education is imperative to patients' self-care at home (Suplee et al., 2016b). They play an important role in reminding patients and other clinicians to monitor BP in frequent intervals to assess optimal measurements and watch for signs of preeclampsia (JC, 2019).

Currently, the unit nurses teach patients about breastfeeding, postpartum blues and depression, incisional care, perineum care, diet intake in relation to breastfeeding, and how to care for newborns (Kaiser Permanente, 2020). Nurses on that postpartum unit are yet to adhere to the JC perinatal standards and guidelines by educating all patients on postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia upon discharge regardless of their diagnosis. Therefore, the unit nurses need to be educated on the updated JC standards so they, in turn, can teach patients to detect signs and symptoms of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia.

Discharge education is populated by the Health Connect Epic electronic system of the hospital based on each patient's symptoms and diagnosis (Kaiser Permanente, 2020). Therefore, with the guidance of this system, only patients diagnosed with preeclampsia receive more education on the subject at discharge. Additionally, patients do not receive consistent education as some nurses may deliver the entire discharge instructions, whereas others highlight perceived important points, indicating the need for standardized discharge education.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this QI project was to develop, implement and evaluate a nurse education program related to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia using the guide of the new JC perinatal standard. In this project, I aimed to (a) examine changes in nurses' knowledge about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia and self-efficacy regarding the use of evidence-based practices, the new JC perinatal standard, after the completion of an educational intervention among postpartum nurses in an acute care setting in Los Angeles County in Southern California; (b) assess readmission rates before and after implementing the educational intervention; (c) identify the extent to which patients will be receiving postpartum education after the completion of the

educational intervention; and (d) develop an education protocol that follows the new JC perinatal standard.

Framework

The Iowa Model

Research relies on theories to provide a methodology for the implementation of a project (Masters, 2014). These theories are central in nursing education, research, treatment, and care of patients. The Iowa Model is a frequently used theoretical framework that supports the implementation of change. The change is often needed to improve patient care or practice (Masters, 2014).

The Iowa Model of Evidence Based Practice was utilized to guide this QI project. The primary purpose of the Iowa Model is to guide practitioners in the use of evidence-based practices (EBP) to improve patient care and health outcomes (Titler et al., 1994). The model discusses the use of seven steps and three decision points designed to implement and evaluate EBP that target a change (Cullen et al., 2018). The Iowa Model was developed by Marita G. Titler and seven of her colleagues at the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics in the early 1990s to aid nurses in using research outcomes to help develop better patient care (Titler et al., 1994). This model calls for the application of research in identifying a problem and its triggers to develop an intervention that will address the patients' needs and create a positive outcome (Cullen et al., 2018; Titler et al., 1994).

The Iowa model was revised in 2015 because of its continued use and implementation in clinical settings to address problems related to patient care and infrastructure (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). Due to its extensive use across the world, researchers have been able to improve the model in the areas of piloting, implementation, patient engagement and sustainment

of change over time (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). This model continues to be utilized in nursing care to incorporate research findings into practice (Cullen et al., 2018). This section will discuss the seven steps of the Iowa Model, how it applied to this QI project, and its uses in research and practice.

Steps of the Iowa Model

The first step of the Iowa Model is to identify a problem and its triggers (Cullen et al., 2018). The problem can be a knowledge-focused or problem-focused trigger that requires change to address the identified problem (Cullen et al., 2018). A knowledge-focused trigger can be related to new standards in practice or new information, which has caused the problem. Whereas a problem-focused trigger is caused by new data that has identified that a problem exists. In identifying the problem, the project lead will explore the triggering events from the perspective of stakeholders who will be the individuals that have a vested interest in the outcome of the project and have experience with the problem (Cullen et al., 2018).

The second step of the model is to state the purpose or questions that will address the identified problem. The project lead must determine if the problem is a priority for the organization (Cullen et al., 2018). The problem must be agreed upon by the unit as a priority for practice change (Titler & Titler, 2001). The determination of a priority is often related to patient morbidity and mortality. The first decision point in the model is the determination of whether the problem is a priority to the organization. If the problem is not a priority, then the project should be abandoned, and another problem should be identified. Other indications that affect the decision to move forward are patient safety, if leadership supports the idea, if resources are available, and if data are available to evaluate the topic (Cullen et al., 2018).

Once the purpose has been identified, an interdisciplinary team is formed to address the problem and assist in facilitating the EBP change, which is the third step. The formation of the team is designed to gather stakeholders who can brainstorm ideas and search the topic based upon their direct knowledge of the problem (Cullen et al., 2018). Team members help guide and support the implementation of the practice change through their knowledge and expertise of the problem and organization (Lacerenza et al., 2018). The team should be interdisciplinary and have a leader that can influence the staff to participate in the change. Nursing leaders can support the use of EBP by allowing nurses time away from patient care to engage in EBP activities and meetings (Lacerenza et al., 2018). The team has the responsibility to formulate, implement and evaluate EBP (Cullen et al., 2018). The team has a level of expertise that enables them to critically appraise and synthesize the available evidence to conduct a literature review, which is the fourth step of the model. The literature review involves gathering, evaluating, and synthesizing the literature related to the problem to obtain the latest EBPs that will be used to implement the project. Once the team has gathered evidence, it may proceed to design a pilot program that will be used to create a practice change in step five. However, the team needs determine whether there is sufficient evidence, which is the second decision point in the model. If there is sufficient evidence to support the change, the team can advance to step five.

The fifth step is when the change in practice is piloted before the adoption, which entails the following steps: (a) developing outcomes to be achieved such as engaging patients and their preferences; (b) considering resources, constraints, and approval; (c) developing a localized protocol; (d) creating an evaluation plan; (e) collecting baseline data; (f) developing an implementation plan; (g) preparing clinicians and materials; (h) promoting adoption; and (i) collecting and reporting post-pilot data (Titler & Titler, 2001). The pilot helps to determine

whether the change can be implemented on a larger scale based upon the improvement made on a smaller scale. The design of the pilot includes consideration of resources available to support its implementation as well as the constraints or limitations that may impede the pilot from moving forward. Once the pilot is designed, a method evaluation must be outlined to determine the effectiveness of the EBP change. This includes training the staff who will be involved with the EBP change on how to implement and promote it. The third decision point in the model is the determination if the change is appropriate for adoption in practice. Gathering and comparing baseline data gathered after the EBP change has been implemented is required to determine if the change can be adopted full scale, system wide.

The sixth step entails the integration and sustainment of the practice change to ensure that change is implemented effectively. As a result, key stakeholders should be identified to facilitate the sustainment of the EBP change (Cullen et al., 2018). The change should also be integrated into the system using quality control improvements. The seventh step is dissemination of the results of the pilot project so that the new EBP is shared with the appropriate parties and the larger community. The goal is to ensure the results are shared in a manner that facilitates continued research and implementation of the practice change to improve patient care (Cullen et al., 2018). Dissemination of the results can be done through presentations during unit and hospital meetings and at conferences, leading to publication of the findings in a reputable journal, so the practice change is shared beyond the organization.

Figure 1

Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care

Application of Iowa Model to Current Project

In this QI project, the problem was identified as the need for EBP change to incorporate the JC perinatal standards related to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia into nursing and patient education to improve patient health outcomes and nursing care on a postpartum unit in a hospital in Southern California.

The first step of the Iowa Model is to identify a problem resulted from a triggering event. According to Titler and Titler (2001), a triggering event is a problem that needs to be corrected due to risks to patient care. For this project, the problem identified, involved the need to implement the JC perinatal standard to reduce morbidity and readmission rates related to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. Therefore, the postpartum unit of this project needed to comply with the third and sixth elements of the JC perinatal standard focusing on patient and nurse education. According to the ACOG (2019), comprehensive nursing education is a strategy that can reduce preventable readmissions. An observational audit conducted at the hospital for the project revealed that there was an increase in the number of readmissions on a postpartum unit over a three-month period (Kaiser Permanente Perinatal Logbook, 2019). This audit was the trigger to identify the problem, calling for this QI project.

The second step of the Iowa Model is to state the purpose of the project. The purpose of this QI project was to develop, implement and evaluate a nurse education program that follows the new JC perinatal standard related to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia to standardize teaching practices among nurses on a postpartum unit in an acute care setting in Los Angeles County in Southern California. The priority was to ensure that the hospital was in alignment with the new perinatal JC standards that were becoming mandatory in January 2021 since this standard can enhance patient safety and health outcomes.

The third step is to form a team whose members have a vested interest in the outcome to evaluate the problem. The interdisciplinary team for this project consisted of the Maternal Child Champions including the director of the postpartum unit, the project author, also two additional charge nurses on the unit, the nurse educator, the nurse manager, an assistant manager, and a team leader with a Doctor of Philosophy degree. A well-constructed timeline was developed to assist in delegating appropriate tasks among the team members.

The fourth step involved gathering, synthesizing, and appraising evidence about the problem, lack of compliance with the new JC perinatal standard related to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, and about effective interventions to address the problem including a nursing education program. A variety of databases were explored for possible research articles related to the topics identified in step four. Key terms were used to conduct the literature search. The literature selected were no more than five years old and consisted of randomized control trials, experimental, and quasi experimental studies, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses. The evidence was collected, synthesized, appraised, and evaluated for its appropriateness to the project.

The fifth step of the Iowa Model entails designing and piloting the practice change to address the identified problem (Titler & Titler, 2001). This project engaged postpartum nurses, the target population of this project. A nursing education program was developed to teach all postpartum nurses, including the newly hired, about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. The program also taught nurses how to effectively educate all their patients about this issue. The next step is to consider the resources, constraints, and approval. The resources available to assist in the implementation of the program such as handouts and education pamphlets were considered.

The director of the unit granted her approval and support for the project since it was in alignment with organizational priorities.

The sixth step addressed implementation strategies to integrate and sustain the new teaching practice into the postpartum unit. The nursing educational program was piloted on the postpartum unit and then evaluated upon its completion. The intervention can be modified based on the target population's feedback and challenges. If shown to be effective, a decision was made about adopting the practice to other postpartum units within the organization. The seventh step involved presenting the results to the postpartum director and the unit managers and nurses during the postpartum unit and hospital meetings. The director determined if the pilot can be used on a larger scale. Once the change is adopted into the other units, the findings could then be shared with other facilities within the organizations and perhaps with other community organizations in the near future. The results may be shared at local, regional, and national conferences.

Use of Iowa Model in Research and Practice

The Iowa Model has been used as a guiding framework in several research studies. It was used to support studies that examined and implemented a practice change related to skin-to-skin contact between infants and their mothers (Boyd, 2017; Haxton et al., 2012). Boyd used the Iowa Model to describe the step-by-step approach used with a group of labor and delivery nurses to include the practice of skin-to-skin contact for women who delivered via cesarean birth to improve mother and infant attachment during cesarean births. In step one of the Iowa Model, initiation of skin-to-skin contact was identified as a knowledge trigger, since nurses were unaware of the positive effect that this technique can have on the mother infant bond. In step two, the researchers described the purpose of the project as improving mother and infant

attachment. The need to improve the mother/infant attachment was deemed a priority for the organization. Step three of the Iowa Model involved the forming a team of labor and delivery nurses, midwives, and a neonatologist, who brainstormed ideas to ensure that the project would be successful. In step four, the project leader met with the team to discuss evidence and the available literature gathered for the project. Sufficient evidence was appraised, reviewed, and noted. A flyer was created for the patients and the nurses to educate them about skin-to-skin contact and its relation to improving mother/infant attachment. Participants were also given a questionnaire regarding any potential challenges they may face with implementing the new technique. The change was deemed appropriate for the facility. The results were evaluated and disseminated by the team and the director to the rest of the labor and delivery unit.

Similarly, Haxton et al. (2012) used the Iowa model to guide the implementation of skin-to-skin contact between new mothers and their babies immediately after birth. Early skin-to-skin contact was identified as the knowledge trigger. The nurses in the study were unaware of the benefits of skin-to-skin contact for both the mother and newborn. The purpose was clearly stated as the need to improve maternal-infant health outcomes. The topic was considered a priority for the organization since they were attempting to become baby friendly. The team was led by the birth centers clinical nurse specialist, which is step three of the Iowa Model (Haxton et al., 2012). Other members of the team included the labor and delivery nurses, lactation consultants, physicians, and certified nursing assistants. All these individuals were identified as having knowledge that would support implementation of the practice change. The clinical nurse specialist compiled and reviewed the research literature, and evidence that addressed the topic of skin-to-skin contact and its outcomes. The articles were distributed to the team members and several discussions took place regarding the best practices identified in them. The evidence

helped facilitate the development of the study, which led to step five which included designing and piloting the change. The clinical nurse specialist provided the education to the labor and delivery staff with the use of four educational sessions via PowerPoint and DVD presentations. The education involved information on the need for immediate skin to skin contact for mother and infant to help improve the bond between them. During this step, nurses were given an opportunity to discuss concerns about the new practice. The change was determined as important for meeting the needs of improving the bond between new mothers and their infants. Steps six and seven were fulfilled through integration and evaluation of the practice change. The results showed an increase in the number of mothers engaging in the practice of immediate skin to skin contact after birth. The Iowa Model provided a sound foundation for both studies and demonstrated how the model can guide a study from start to finish.

Numerous studies have used the Iowa Model to implement an EBP change. A group of oncology nurses implemented a practice change to prevent falls while the patients were in an inpatient stem cell transplantation unit (Brown, 2014). The nurses were concerned with the high number of falls that were occurring among the patients in the unit, causing injury (Brown, 2014). The team used the Iowa Model to guide the process in identifying and implementing a new practice change (Brown, 2014). The group of oncology nurses formed a fall prevention team, which also included physicians, nurses, physical therapists, and occupational therapist (Brown, 2014). The team identified the literature that supported the use of patients wearing brightly colored non-skid socks (Brown, 2014). The socks were piloted on two of the units and were deemed a success, as they were helpful in decreasing the number of falls on the two units. Ultimately, the new practice was implemented across the entire hospital since the new practice led to a decrease in number of falls, which is also cost effective (Brown, 2014).

To decrease the mortality rate related to sepsis at a hospital, a group of emergency room nurses implemented a practice change supported by the Iowa model (Tedesco et al., 2017). Patients at that hospital received inconsistent protocols of medical treatment, which was a concern. A multidisciplinary team was formed that consisted of emergency room nurses, personnel from the laboratory, pharmacy, critical care, and medical surgical nursing units as well as leadership. After reviewing evidence from the literature, the team developed an intervention plan to address sepsis management using an algorithm tool. The tool provided a standard practice for nurses and providers to treat patients diagnosed with sepsis. The tool included specific labs to draw and medications to give. The step-by-step algorithm was successful, leading to a decrease in the mortality rate, which was reduced from 18.4% in 2015 to 13.2% in 2016 (Tedesco et al., 2017).

In support of these studies, a group of nurses at a children's hospital used the Iowa Model to implement a practice change to decrease the morbidity and mortality of low-birth-weight infants due to the nursing practice of flushing and drawing blood from the infant umbilical artery catheters [UAC] (Gordon et al., 2008). The nurses were concerned with the increased mortality rate and using different techniques when providing nursing procedures and maintenance care to infants with UACs, which may lead to harm. A multidisciplinary team was formed to examine the current practice process. The team reviewed the relevant literature and found that rapid blood draws and flushes can lead to intraventricular hemorrhage and periventricular leukomalacia, which could be potentially fatal; therefore, a standard practice was developed and followed, leading to a decrease in the mortality rate. The researchers skipped the pilot study step because of the high level of research studies found. The new practice was immediately created and put into place (Gordon et al., 2008).

The Iowa model was also used to guide the development, implementation, and evaluation of a pilot nursing educational intervention to promote an evidence-based transition from gavage feeding directly to breastfeeding in the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) at a hospital in Canada (Ziadi et al., 2016). There was an increase in the number of infants developing necrotizing enterocolitis, infection, sepsis, and readmissions. The unit did not have a written formal policy related to direct breastfeeding after gavage feeding or a standardized practice. A multidisciplinary team, composed of a NICU nurse educator, lactation consultants, nutritionist, and clinical nurse specialist, developed and implemented an educational program to teach about the benefits of direct breastfeeding in preterm infants. The results showed there was an improvement in beliefs and knowledge regarding direct breastfeeding after gavage feeding after completion of the educational intervention (Ziadi et al., 2016).

The Iowa Model was a good fit for the project since the project involved the use of an EBP change that was piloted before it was implemented on a larger scale. The Iowa Model provided a sequence of steps that were used to guide the development, implementation, and evaluation of this QI project. The aim was to reinforce the new JC perinatal standard and educate nurses on postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. The model also provided and discussed the necessary elements that must be available to enhance the success rates of the project and its sustainability. The seven steps of the Iowa Model guided the problem identification process and its triggers for the project. The model was further used to design and implement a nursing education program to address the knowledge gap among nurses. The project outcome was to positively change the practice of postpartum nurses using EBP to enhance patient safety and improve quality of care.

Review of Literature

The purpose of this project was to develop, implement, and evaluate the effectiveness of a nursing education program regarding postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. The literature review addresses and appraises the current evidence regarding postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia and the proposed education utilizing the JC new perinatal standard. Numerous electronic databases were explored including PubMed, CINAHL, Ovid, Science Direct, Google Scholar and Cochrane Library. The search was limited to peer-reviewed academic journals, written in English, and published between 2014 and 2020. The search terms used included *postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia*, *readmissions due to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia*, *nursing education*, *patient education*, *evidence-based guidelines about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia*, and *the new JC perinatal standard*, and *data-driven* or *evidence based*. The studies were excluded if they were case studies, editorials, books, magazines, or newspaper articles. Articles focusing on pharmacological therapy to treat postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia alone were also excluded. The key terms were combined to *postpartum hypertension and postpartum preeclampsia* along with the Boolean phrase *and* to include *readmissions*, *complications*, and *education*.

The literature searches yielded 694 articles, the vast majority of which were excluded since they failed to meet the inclusion criteria or were related to drug treatment alone. Therefore, 32 studies were included in this literature review. Thirty of which were quantitative, one was qualitative (Suplee et al., 2016a) and one was a mix method study (Malagon-Maldonado et al., 2017).

Risk Factors of Postpartum Hypertension and Preeclampsia

Risk factors of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, such as race, obesity, BMI greater than 30 kg/m², lifestyle habits such as smoking, exercise, and diet must be discussed with patients (Skurniket et al., 2017). These risk factors have been investigated and identified in research. Perdiago et al. (2020) conducted a secondary analysis of a randomized controlled trial that utilized a text message-based home BP monitoring system in 84 postpartum women. The study evaluated postpartum BP trends and the time to resolve hypertension among women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, focusing on impact of race and BMI on these trends. Black participants comprised 63% and had a BP increase within 6.5 to seven days after birth. Non-Black women with a BMI of less than 35 kg/m² had steady decreases in systolic BP, whereas other groups peaked around 6.5 days postpartum. The results also showed that 81% of non-Black women had resolution of hypertension versus 49% in Black women (Perdiago et al., 2020).

Similarly, in a case control study, Redman et al. (2019) investigated clinical risk factors associated with the development of delayed onset postpartum preeclampsia and found that in comparison to women in the control group, 18% were Black, 20.1% were obese, and 25.8% delivered by cesarean section. Skurnik et al. (2017) and Takaoka et al. (2016) supported these results, in case control and retrospective cohort studies respectively, in which BMI greater than 30kg/m² was recognized as a significant risk factor for postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia.

Vilchez et al. (2016) proposed that there may be a difference in clinical presentation and pregnancy outcomes between women with antepartum preeclampsia and those with a new onset postpartum preeclampsia. This retrospective study researchers recruited 184 patients to compare 92 women with antepartum preeclampsia to 92 with new onset of postpartum preeclampsia (Vilchez et al., 2016). These results showed that symptoms including generalized swelling, new

visual problems, severe headache, shortness of breath, nausea and vomiting, abdominal pain, elevated BPs, seizures, and pedal edema presented more severely in new onset postpartum preeclampsia (Vilchez et al., 2016).

Goel et al. (2015) had 988 consecutive women admitted to a tertiary medical center for a cesarean section for single pregnancies to determine factors associated with the risk of developing postpartum hypertension. Biomarkers associated with preeclampsia, such as angiogenic factors soluble fms-like tyrosine kinase 1 and placental growth factor, were monitored. Participants with higher biomarkers were found to positively correlate with higher BPs in postpartum. Of the 988 women, 184 women (18.6%) developed postpartum hypertension and 77 (7.79%) developed de novo hypertension occurring after delivery through six weeks postpartum. The remainder of the participants had a hypertensive disorder of pregnancy during the antepartum period. In addition, a higher BMI and a history of diabetes mellitus were found to be associated with the development of postpartum hypertension.

Bigelow et al. (2014) aimed to identify risk factors associated with patient characteristics for new onset late postpartum preeclampsia in a case control study. The researchers compared 34 women with new onset late postpartum preeclampsia to 68 women who did not have this disorder. The results found that new onset late postpartum preeclampsia was associated with age greater than 40 years, being Black and Latino, obese, and have diabetes mellitus.

Based on the aforementioned studies, risk factors for postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia includes the Black and Hispanic race, obesity, increased BMI of 30 or more, smoking, drinking alcohol, and comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus type II and gestational diabetes, immune disorders, in vitro fertilization, advanced maternal age, and history of preeclampsia (Bigelow et al., 2014; Perdiago et al., 2020; Redman et al., 2019; Skurnik et al.,

2017). Such results highlight the significance of educating postpartum patients about these symptoms to prevent complications and death since early identification can lead to treating the disorder in a timely manner.

Readmission Due to Postpartum Hypertension/Preeclampsia

In the U.S., hospital readmission rates have emerged as a vital measure for quality of care (Wagner et al., 2019). Reduction in hospital readmissions represents an enhancement in the quality of care provided to patients, indicating avoidable complications (Hirshberg et al., 2016; Howard-Anderson et al., 2016; Wagner et al., 2019). Additionally, reduction in hospital readmissions is linked to lower costs in healthcare, which accounts for almost half of all healthcare expenses (Wagner et al., 2019).

Readmissions are defined as any patient readmitted to the hospital within 30 days after being discharged in the adult medical surgical patient units (Howard-Anderson et al., 2016). However, readmissions for postpartum patients are defined as being readmitted within six weeks after being discharged from giving birth (Mogos et al., 2018). Giving birth is a major reason for hospitalization of females who are of childbearing age (Mogos et al., 2018; Wagner et al., 2019;). In 2013–2014, there were approximately 6.3 million deliveries of which 10.6 % were complicated by hypertension disorders during pregnancy (Mogos et al., 2018;Wagner et al., 2019;). After delivery, women were readmitted to the hospital for postpartum complications such as postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia (Mogos et al., 2018). Among the pregnancies complicated by hypertension disorders of pregnancy (HDP), there was a 2.5–4.6% increase in readmissions within six weeks related to gestational hypertension and superimposed preeclampsia (Mogos et al., 2018). Postpartum readmissions resulted in significant burdens incurred by the mother and the healthcare system (Mogos et al., 2018). Postpartum readmissions

contribute to disruptions in family bonding since the mother is taken away from caring for her newborn due to rehospitalization in addition to significant emotional and societal burdens (Aseltine et al., 2015; Mogos et al., 2018; Wagner et al., 2019).

Johnson et al. (2019) used a cross-sectional analysis utilizing a national inpatient sample to examine the rate of severe maternal morbidity among postpartum readmissions and to identify potential risk factors. The researchers identified 27,668,757 delivery hospitalizations and 430,625 postpartum readmissions that occurred during 2006–2012, for a readmission rate of 1.6%. Out of the 430,625 patients 61,609 (14.31%) were readmitted with a hypertensive disorder (Johnson et al., 2019). The researchers found that postpartum readmissions complicated by severe maternal morbidity were disproportionately high among women 35 years and older, non-Hispanic Blacks, women with pre-existing medical conditions, and women admitted to hospitals in the southern region of the US (Johnson et al., 2019).

Mogos et al. (2018) used a retrospective study by utilizing a nationwide readmission database in the United States of 666,506 women to examine factors associated with potentially preventable postpartum readmissions following HDP complicated pregnancies. The findings suggested that 1 in every 9 pregnancies experienced HDP complications. Also, women with HDP complicated pregnancies were at risk of readmission since they experienced more complications than women with non-HDP pregnancies. Postpartum readmission rates were found to be highest for gestations that were impacted negatively by superimposed preeclampsia complicated by severe preeclampsia. Early hospital readmissions among women were linked to cesarean childbirth, Medicare and Medicaid, and the existence of one or more illnesses (Mogos et al., 2018).

Brousseau et al. (2017) used a retrospective cohort study to describe the characteristics of women diagnosed with postpartum hypertension in an emergency department (ED) to better inform postpartum care. Women with an ED diagnosis of hypertension were compared to those who presented for ED care. Over a six-month period, 52 out of 252 women were readmitted with postpartum hypertension; older age and a BMI greater than 30 were identified as readmission risk factors.

Readmissions related to postpartum issues have gained national attention in the last 10 years due to their high cost (Mogos et al., 2018). Readmissions after childbirth may have detrimental consequences for both the facility and the new parents. For the facility, there may be lack of reimbursement, whereas the parent may get an extremely high bill. In 2015, the HRRP was enacted as part of the Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act. The HRRP program allows CMS to track readmissions and impose penalties on hospitals with readmission rates that exceeded the risk adjusted calculated national average (CMS, 2020). For the family, financial stress due to the mother not being able to work and the significant other having to care for the newborn (Mogos et al., 2018; Wagner et al., 2019). Hirshberg et al. (2016) found that there was an increased risk of postpartum readmissions due to hypertension, diabetes, wound and uterine infections, and deep vein thrombosis. Patients readmitted after discharge cost the hospital approximately \$731 million (Hirshberg et al., 2016; Mogos et al., 2018).

Researchers identified and examined readmission as an outcome. Tran et al. (2020) employed a retrospective design to compare process outcomes, such as readmission, among three groups including antepartum preeclampsia without postpartum preeclampsia (APNP), antepartum preeclampsia with persistent postpartum preeclampsia (APYP) and new onset postpartum preeclampsia (NEWYP). The study had 43 participants in the APNP group, 59

participants in the APYP group, and 18 participants in the NEWYP group. The results showed that NEWYP had higher odds for readmission, higher systolic BP, and greater values of serum creatinine compared to both APYP and APNP.

Similarly, Wen et al. (2020) identified readmission as an outcome associated with fragmentation in which 21,789 out of 141,276 postpartum readmissions occurred at a hospital different from the place of delivery. It was also found that fragmentation was less likely for hypertension (11.1%), wound complications (10.7%), and uterine infections (11%), and more likely for heart failure (28.6%), thromboembolism (28.4%), and upper respiratory infections (33.9%).

These outcomes indicate that educating postpartum patients should focus on the NEWYP patient population that may have severe clinical presentation in comparison to APYP and APNP; those patients need to be aware of reporting any changes promptly. Also, postpartum women need to know that it may be beneficial for them to return to the hospital where the delivery occurred if they need medical care after discharge, providing continuity of care. Healthcare providers, in this case, have access to the previous medical record for antepartum, labor and delivery, and postpartum, which prompts them to identify a change more efficiently.

Factors Associated with Postpartum Readmission

Numerous studies examined factors related to postpartum readmissions, such as race, socioeconomic status, age, and comorbidities (Aziz et al., 2020; Clapp et al., 2016; Johnson et al., 2019; Mogos et al., 2018; Wagner et al., 2019). Wagner et al. used a retrospective study of all singleton deliveries in Florida, California, New York, and Maryland from the State Inpatient Databases Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project. The study used 4,999,993 patients to evaluate the effect of social determinants of health on postpartum readmissions in all postpartum patients

and in a subgroup analysis of those with a diagnosis of preeclampsia. Patients readmitted were more likely Black, in the poorest quartile of median income, and with public insurance, Medicare or Medicaid.

In support of these results, Aziz et al. (2020) conducted a cross-sectional analysis utilizing a national inpatient sample from the Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project from 2012–2014. The study was conducted to determine the association of race with serious complications during postpartum readmissions. The study used 207,730 participants out of 11.3 million births. Compared to non-Hispanic White women, non-Hispanic Black women were at 80% greater risk of postpartum readmission whereas Hispanic women were at 11% lower risk of readmission (Aziz et al., 2020).

Clapp et al. (2018) used a cross-sectional study utilizing state inpatient databases in the United States. The three states selected were California, Florida, and New York. The researchers used 114,748 patients who were readmitted during postpartum. The purposes of this study were to describe the trends in postpartum readmissions overtime, to characterize the common indications and associated diagnosis for readmissions, and to determine maternal, delivery, and hospital characteristics that may be associated with readmissions. The purpose of the study was to determine if the increasing rate of postpartum readmissions was related to caesarean sections. The study's findings showed that readmission rates increased from 1.72% in 2004 to 2.16% in 2011. Readmitted patients were more likely to be publicly insured, to be Black, to have comorbidities, such as hypertension, diabetes, and to have had a cesarean delivery. The researchers found that the increasing rate of caesarean deliveries did not explain the increasing rate of postpartum readmissions. However, the increasing postpartum readmission rate appeared to be related to maternal comorbidities such as obesity, chronic hypertension, psychiatric disease,

and diabetes (Clapp et al., 2018). Caesarean childbirth was linked to increased readmissions in another study (Mogos et al., 2018). Comorbidities are important risk factors associated with postpartum readmissions (Clapp et al., 2018; Johnson et al., 2019); therefore, nurses must incorporate in their education to postpartum patients during admission and upon discharge, following the guidelines of the JC new perinatal standard.

Contrary to the findings about the Hispanic ethnicity by Aziz et al. (2020), Aseltine et al. (2015) found that being Hispanic was a risk-factor for readmission pertaining to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. The study's researchers used a retrospective study utilizing a statewide database maintained by the Connecticut Department of Public Health and included 167,857 participants. The study aimed to examine 30-day readmission rates after vaginal and cesarean delivery by race, ethnicity, and insurance status. The results showed that there were higher rates of readmissions among Black and Hispanic women compared to White women (Aseltine et al., 2015). Being of Hispanic ethnicity should not be overlooked by nurses as a risk factor even with these mixed results. Such patients still need to be monitored closely after delivery for six weeks and up to one year.

The association between the mode of delivery and readmission due to postpartum hypertension, in women with pregnancy related hypertension, was also investigated by Hirshberg et al. (2016). The researchers used a case control design in which 25 women were the cases and 74 were the controls. The results suggested that hypertension readmission was not associated with the mode of delivery, but a longer length in labor was a significant factor.

Black women and patients with public insurance, such as Medicaid and Medicare, were at risk for being readmitted with postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia (Aziz et al., 2020; Clapp et al., 2016; Mogos et al., 2018; Wagner et al., 2019), indicating the importance of considering

such factors when designing and implementing patient education programs. Educating postpartum patients to increase their knowledge regarding postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia will empower and motivate them to conduct self-care and seek help when noticing any complications early on. This education should be done in postpartum and the ED to prevent mortality, morbidity, and readmissions.

Nursing Education

Education is empowering as it provides knowledge, confidence, and contributes to the development of interpersonal skills and promotes a healthy lifestyle (Hahn & Truman, 2015). Postpartum education has usually focused on infant care and maternal self-care (Lowdermilk et al., 2015; Suplee et al., 2016b; Suplee et al., 2017). However, postpartum patients should be educated about different aspects of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia (Skurnik et al., 2017). They should be educated about signs and symptoms of the disease which vary from one patient to another. In 2013, the California Maternity Quality Care Collaborative developed guidelines that influenced discharge instructions on postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia (California Department of Health Care Services, 2020). These guidelines emphasized the importance of teaching postpartum women about signs and symptoms of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, which prompts patients to seek medical attention in a timely manner. The guideline for discharge practices includes having a comprehensive and simply written list of symptoms in place to be disseminated to postpartum mothers and supporting family members upon discharge (Banke-Thomas et al., 2019). It is vital to educate these women about such signs and symptoms to achieve early realization of warning signs and to enable implementation of early interventions by healthcare providers to decrease rates of maternal morbidity, a major

concern in the U.S. given the high numbers recorded annually (D'Alton et al., 2014; JC, 2019; Suplee et al., 2016b).

Some patients may experience a headache unrelieved with pain medication (Mahajan et al., 2020; Suplee et al., 2016b; Vilchez et al., 2016). Others may experience blurred vision, epigastric pain, seeing black spots or floaters, and generalized swelling (Bigelow et al., 2014; Redman et al., 2019; Tran et al., 2020; Vilchez et al., 2016). Other signs may include shortness of breath (Mahajan et al., 2020). Postpartum patients also need to be educated that a diagnosis of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia occurs when they have more than two elevated BP's greater than 140/90 measured twice at least four hours apart (Redman et al., 2019; Skurnik et al., 2017). If it is untreated, a severe form of preeclampsia known as eclampsia can develop (Vilchez et al., 2016). Many of the health problems postpartum patients experience after being discharged may be efficaciously treated if they are immediately identified and patients are provided with prompt medical response (Suplee et al., 2016b).

Cohen et al. (2015) used a six-month prospective observational study to assess systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) values during labor and to analyze their predictive value for early postpartum preeclampsia. The study included 1,435 women in labor who had no hypertensive disorder either before or during pregnancy. Both BPs, SBP, and DBP, were measured every 15 minutes during labor and signs of preeclampsia were checked for in the early postpartum period. The study found that the mean values of SBP and DBP were significantly higher during the first stage of labor without any treatment compared to the last prenatal visit. It was found that epidural analgesia had no effect on the SBP and DBP during labor whereas oxytocin moderately increased the BP. Only early postpartum preeclampsia was identified in .9% of the women. Also, a maximum SBP, equal or higher than 150mm/hg, or DBP,

equal or higher than 91mm/hg, during labor were predictive factors of early postpartum preeclampsia. Thus, educating the patient on how to take their own BP properly is crucial in preventing hospital readmissions due to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia (Cohen et al., 2015).

Nursing education is imperative when taking care of postpartum patients. Malagon-Maldonado et al. (2017) found that nursing educational practices were predictive of postpartum mothers' perceptions of readiness for hospital discharge. The researchers conducted a mixed method study of 185 postpartum mothers to explore the antepartum, intrapartum, and postpartum predictors of discharge readiness. The study also found that nurses' teaching skills and the educational content received were significant in patients understanding of discharge instructions. Research investigated many factors influencing postpartum nursing education, such as health literacy, nurses' knowledge, patients' knowledge, availability of educational materials, and methods of teaching.

Logsdon et al. (2018) used a cross sectional study that recruited 120 new mothers who were predominantly low-income women to describe new mothers' knowledge related to maternal mortality. Results revealed that most new mothers knew that they should watch for bleeding, a severe headache, and swelling of the face and the extremities after discharge. However, fewer participants knew that a new mother could experience feelings of harming herself and her newborn, have blood clots larger than her baby's hand, a temperature of 100.4 degrees or higher, and a foul odor with vaginal discharge. The results also indicated that 18% of mothers experiencing these symptoms would take no action, 76.7% would tell their significant other, 72.5% would tell their mother, and 60% would call the labor and delivery unit. Additionally,

38% of the sample knew that postpartum complications could occur up to one year after birth, but 13% reported not knowing that complications can occur for up to six weeks postpartum.

Health literacy is the capability of individuals to acquire, synthesize, and grasp basic health information and services they require in making effective health decisions (Dickens & Piano, 2013; Yen & Leasure, 2019). For patients to be able to understand instructions provided, they need some level of health literacy (Dickens & Piano, 2013; Yen & Leasure, 2019); it is essential to understand that grasping and administering a health care plan developed for persistent diseases is significantly demanding (Yen & Leasure, 2019). It was found that approximately 35 % of Americans have levels of health literacy lower than the intermediate level (Yen & Leasure, 2019). Therefore, it is essential to facilitate oral instructions to healthcare literacy levels of patients to ensure that they can understand and comprehend health information and instructions provided during the admission and upon discharge (Yen & Leasure, 2019). Al-Safi et al. (2011) proposed that instructions about the probability of experiencing deferred preeclampsia and eclampsia should happen after delivery; therefore, healthcare providers in postpartum units and the emergency department need to notice the signs and symptoms of preeclampsia and its progression. They also need to continue educating all postpartum patients about complications of eclampsia to reduce morbidities and mortalities due to this disease (Al-Safi et al., 2011).

As for nurses' knowledge related to postpartum education, Suplee et al. (2017) used a cross-sectional design that recruited 372 postpartum nurses to assess their knowledge of maternal morbidity and mortality and information they shared with women before discharge about identifying potential warning signs of postpartum complications. Participants completed a 25-item electronic survey to assess the nurse's knowledge of the leading causes of maternal

mortality. Fifty four percent of nurse participants were aware of the rising rate of maternal mortality in the US; whereas only 12% accurately reported the percentages of death that occurred during the postpartum period.

A significant quantity of medical information is disremembered instantly after patients are discharged due to the large amount of information presented to patients; some information may be recalled incorrectly (Yen & Leasure, 2019). That prompts the need to implement effective strategies when providing patients with information upon discharge. Methods of delivery of postpartum education were addressed in the literature as they may influence the effectiveness of teaching. According to O'Meara and Lepic (2016), relevant verbal and printed instructive materials should be provided to patients before they are discharged. Plain language communication was identified as an effective strategy for providing education to patients in healthcare settings as the delivery of information should be done simply and succinct to enhance understanding (Warde et al., 2018). On the other hand, teach back as a technique for disseminating discharge directives was recognized for enhancing patients' understanding of the information provided (Howard-Anderson et al., 2016; Yen & Leasure 2019).

Hirshberg et al. (2016) conducted a randomized clinical trial to compare the strength of text-based BP monitoring to in-person visits for women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy in the immediate postpartum period. The study used 206 women with 103 being grouped in the text-based group and 103 being placed in the office-based group. The BP readings were collected via text; the text message group was randomized to two weeks of text-based surveillance using a home BP cuff or attending there four to six-day follow-up appointment in the office. The researchers found that there was a significant increase in BP obtained in the texting group in the first 10 days postpartum compared with the office group, 92.2% and 43%

respectively (Hirshberg et al., 2016). This finding signifies a form of communication that can be effectively used to alert health care providers if patients are experiencing signs and symptoms of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia.

Yen and Leasure (2019) identified the teach-back method as an effective instructional approach, also known as closing the loop. This strategy is widely used in inpatient and outpatient health education programs and interventions (Miller et al., 2016; O'Meara & Lopic, 2016; Yen & Leasure, 2019). The teach-back method is used when paired with educational interventions that range from short instructions to 20-hour programs, suggesting that this strategy can be used to accomplish diverse educational purposes (Yen & Leasure, 2019). Yen and Leasure found that the teach-back strategy improved patients' knowledge and enhances their ability to manage their health concerns although there was limited evidence on healthcare knowledge retention.

Similarly, Suplee et al. (2017) supported teach-back as an effective technique that involves the provision of appropriate information concerning possible complications of pregnancy and childbirth. It also incorporates the use of a checklist that has documentation on if a support person was present during the process of providing education (Suplee et al., 2016b).

In support of these results, Miller et al. (2016) explored patients' perceptions about the teach-back method to facilitate patient education; the study had 30 patients involved in one-on-one conversations in an educational program. Patients had a positive attitude towards learning about their healthcare through this technique. They also appreciated it since it gets them involved in the process and gives them the opportunity to discuss concerns and clarify misconceptions. The majority of the patients, 83.3%, understood their medications and only 6.7% of those patients were readmitted after 30 days (Miller et al., 2016).

In a randomized control trial, Griffey et al. (2015) examined whether the teach-back method could improve comprehension and perceived comprehension of discharge instructions and satisfaction among 408 patients with limited health literacy. Patients completed an audio recorded structured interview evaluating comprehension and perceived comprehension of diagnosis, ED course, post ED care, and reasons to return and patient satisfaction. The study suggested that patients randomized to receive the teach-back method had higher comprehension of ED care including post ED medication, self-care, and follow up instructions. There was no change in patient satisfaction or perceived comprehension.

Logsdon et al. (2018) employed a prospective, quasi experimental design to determine acceptability of simple written educational pamphlets to 123 adolescent mothers to determine efficacy of the simple written education pamphlets in approving adolescent mothers' knowledge related to breastfeeding, infant care, postpartum depression, and mother-infant relationship to determine if the mother would retain higher knowledge scores after a two-week period. Participants completed a pre- and post-test about postpartum care. The post-test was given immediately after education and a second post-test was given two weeks later. The study indicated that these mothers found the pamphlets written in simple educational material to be acceptable and the intervention was initially effective in improving knowledge scores in all content areas. However, the knowledge was not retained as the scores were not significantly different from baseline at the two-week assessment.

Qualitative data explored types of educational materials and discharge information being currently used by postpartum nurses (Suplee et al., 2016a). Suplee et al., (2016b) aimed to educate women about warning signs of postpartum complications and what key messages should be presented to women after birth and before discharge. The study recruited 52 postpartum

nurses to conduct six focus group discussions using a semi structured interview guide to elicit data on how and what nurses taught women about maternal post-birth warning signs. The focus group discussions were audio-taped, transcribed, coded, and clustered into categories. It was found that an absence of standard guidance and procedures on how nurses address the complexities of teaching patients who are classified as being at risk for maternal illnesses through postpartum complications. To facilitate education during discharge, the study addressed the need to have an educational checklist tool and standardized patient education in place as part of the discharge process was discussed. Such educational tools are imperative to educate women on the possible complications they may face in the postpartum period. Furthermore, it is important for all postpartum patients to be engaged in focused discussions concerning life-threatening after-birth complications as part of the discharge routine. One of the potential challenges is to ensure the availability of an environment where nurses can empower women with the necessary information without instilling fear in them (Suplee, Kleppel, & Bingham, 2016a).

The aforementioned studies addressed the type of knowledge that should be utilized to thoroughly educate postpartum patients about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia during admission and upon discharge as the education process should be on-going. They also suggested some effective methods of delivery to enhance patient education, comprehension, and retention of the knowledge, all of which were integrated in the nurse educational program to be designed for this QI project.

Joint Commission Perinatal Standard and Related Education

The JC has introduced new elements of performance (EP) necessary to ensure the achievement of quality care to patients (JC, 2019). The EPs were created to enhance the quality

and safety of care for all stages of gestation and post-delivery. The changes were prompted by the high ranking of the US among developed countries for maternal deaths as the US is ranked 65th among developed countries (JC, 2019). Preeclampsia related mortality can be prevented. A retrospective study (Main et al., 2015) compared specific maternal and clinical characteristics and contributing factors to pregnancy-related mortality to develop focused clinical and public health prevention programs. The study analyzed 207 pregnancy related deaths. Medical records, autopsy reports, and coroner reports were reviewed by a multidisciplinary team to determine the cause of death, clinical and demographic characteristics, chance to alter outcome, contributing factors, and quality improvement opportunities. The researchers found that the five leading causes of pregnancy-related deaths were cardiovascular disease, preeclampsia or eclampsia, hemorrhage, venous thromboembolism, and amniotic fluid embolism. Ultimately, there was a good chance to alter the outcome in 41% of deaths with highest rates of preventability among hemorrhage (70%), and preeclampsia (60%).

The JC, (2019) carried out an evaluation of expert literature to develop national guidelines for postpartum education in the country. The review of the literature provided an understanding of essential areas that hold the most impact in terms of improving maternal death rates in the country; therefore, the JC developed the new EP to guide healthcare providers on how to educate themselves and their patients on issues concerning preeclampsia and to provide education to all nursing staff responsible for providing care to pregnant and postpartum patients concerning the hemorrhage procedure in the hospital (JC 2019).

The minimum education needs to be provided during nursing orientation and biennially to ensure that care teams function optimally during an emergency (JC, 2019). The new EP requires role specific education and training for staff responsible for caring about laboring and

postpartum patients in a healthcare facility. The role specific education and training should address the procedures involved in hypertension/preeclampsia in the hospital to ensure BP is reduced through rapid recognition and treatment which will, in turn, reduce maternal morbidity and mortality. The staff will be able to provide evidence-based treatment once they recognize the related health condition. In addition, simulation trainings are needed to provide staff with training on hospital procedures in real environments (JC, 2019).

The EP also provided many guidelines of education and training (JC, 2019). Patients and their families must be provided with printed education. The education should also be provided to the designated support persons in instances where that is possible. The minimum requirements for what should be incorporated in printed education includes signs and manifestations of acute and severe high BP and preeclampsia in the process of hospitalization and after discharge. Patients learn that this information should alert and prompt them to seek immediate care (JC, 2019).

Education should also be provided to patients on follow-up appointments and when to call for urgent and emergent situations (JC, 2019). According to the JC (2019), the rationale for the guideline on patient education is prompted by maternal mortality reviews. The reviews indicate that certain patients experience extreme postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia because they are not cognizant of the signs and symptoms (JC, 2019). Therefore, it is vital that patients comprehend their preeclampsia diagnosis and be able to inform physicians about their gestational history when they seek care after discharge (Maric-Bilkan et al., 2019). This type of education can ensure accurate diagnosis and management of the illness, especially in instances of fragmented postpartum readmission (Maric-Bilkan et al., 2019).

Levine et al. (2016) conducted a retrospective cohort study to determine demographics and clinical factors associated with low six-week postpartum follow-up rates among women with preeclampsia with severe features. Over half of the women went for their six-week follow-up appointment; however, African American women and those who completed five or less prenatal visits were the least likely to follow-up (Levine et al., 2016)

Suplee et al. (2017) found that there was an absence of standard guidance and procedures on how nurses should address the complexities of teaching patients classified as being at risk for maternal illnesses through postpartum complications. Also, there was a lack of available guidelines concerning women at risk because of their postpartum health status (Suplee et al., 2017).

Patient Perceptions toward Education and Readiness to Learn

Postpartum patients' preparedness and readiness to learn is exhibited through their capacity to remember the information provided which may be more than what the postpartum patient can learn (Bastable, 2017). Postpartum patients may perceive they have received a satisfactory and high-quality education (Lindpaintner et al., 2013; Weiss & Lokken, 2009); however, Logsdon et al. (2018) found that new mothers retained some postpartum information but not all of the information that was taught. Postpartum patients are usually fatigued; therefore, spending a long period of time educating them can lead to negative outcomes (McCarter-Spaulding & Shea, 2016). It is recommended to briefly address important issues at the beginning of prenatal visits, continue educating them during hospitalization, and reinforce that education post discharge to ensure effective education (McCarter-Spaulding & Shea, 2016).

Upon examining patients' perceptions of the discharge process, Howard-Anderson et al. (2016) found that patients who held a negative perception regarding being discharged were more

likely to be readmitted, concluding that patients who lack readiness to be discharged also lack readiness to receive discharge education. Out of 230 patients who participated in the study, 65% remembered reviewing discharge instructions, but 22% could not remember critical information on the paperwork. Approximately, 28% reported not being ready for discharge due to inadequate symptom resolution, poor pain control, and concerns about self-care (Howard-Anderson et al., 2016).

Timing of education can be crucial to ensure its effectiveness. McCarter-Spaulding and Shea (2016) did not find a significant relationship between providing education and the prevention of postpartum depression. The study suggested that this lack of association can be attributed to the timing of education. Timing of education offers insight into the readiness of patients to get educated before discharged. Selecting the appropriate time to enhance patient education may explain the limited role of education in changing health outcomes after patients have been discharged. Patients are faced with many distractions as they juggle physical recovery, entertaining visitors, infant care, and patient acuity. Additionally, caregivers are distracted as they attempt to help patients balance different aspects. These disruptions have a negative impact on discharge teaching provided to postpartum women by caregivers (McCarter-Spaulding & Shea, 2016).

Felix et al. (2015) surveyed 587 patients readmitted to an adult inpatient unit within 30 days. Approximately 74% held positive perceptions related to discharge goals, suggesting that they were ready to receive information about signs and symptoms that they needed to watch for. Four out of 5 patients reported that the information provided to them made them understand how to take care of themselves once they were discharged. Patients also reported understanding their prescribed medications and getting their prescriptions filled and gaining critical information

about when to contact healthcare providers if their condition declined. Two thirds of those patients reported having the opportunity to discuss their concerns with physicians or healthcare providers prior to being discharged (Felix et al., 2015). The majority of the participants reported positive experiences receiving the discharge process, which could be attributed to their desire to please the study researchers or to their inability to elaborate because of the way the questions were formulated.

Studies on readiness of the patient to learn were found to be limited upon conducting this literature review. Education has been identified as an effective approach in managing postpartum readmission resulting from hypertension/preeclampsia. Timing of the provision of the information, in most cases, is not optimal as postpartum patients face significant distractions that limit their ability to understand and comprehend the education provided.

Appraisal of the Literature Review

This literature review included 30 quantitative studies consisted of three randomized control trials (Griffey et al., 2015; Hirshberg et al., 2016; Lopes Perdigao et al., 2020), one systematic review (Yen & Leasure, 2019), five case control studies (Bigelow et al., 2014; Hirshberg et al., 2016; Levine et al., 2016; Redman et al., 2019; Skurnik et al., 2017), four cross-sectional studies (Aziz et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2019; Logsdon et al., 2018; Suplee et al., 2016b), one prospective longitudinal study (Cohen et al., 2015), two quasi experimental studies (Logsdon et al., 2018; Spaulding et al., 2016;), 12 retrospective cohort observational studies (Aseltine et al., 2015; Brousseau et al., 2017; Clapp et al., 2016; Felix et al., 2015; Goel et al., 2015; Mogos et al., 2018; Takaoka et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2020; Vilchez et al., 2016; Wagner et al., 2019; Wen et al., 2020), one case series observational study (Main et al., 2015), and one in-

person survey (Howard-Anderson et al., 2016). It also included one mixed method (Malagon-Maldonado et al., 2017) and one qualitative study (Suplee, Kleppel, & Bingham, 2016a).

Sample sizes recruited in these studies varied from small, 34 participants (Bigelow et al., 2014; Skurnik et al., 2017), to large samples, up to 66,000. Studies with large sample sizes provide more reliable results that can be generalized (Polit & Beck, 2017). The majority of the studies took place in the US; two studies were conducted in Japan (Takaoka et al., 2016) and France (Cohen et al., 2015). Data were collected via national databases (Mahajan et al., 2020), inpatient databases, medical records, electronic surveys (Suplee, Kleppel, & Bingham, 2016a), semi-structured interviews, international classification of diseases ninth revision codes, and chart reviews (Bigelow et al., 2014; Redman et al., 2019).

The studies included in the literature review reported limitations. Some of the studies were case controls (Bigelow et al., 2014; Hirshberg et al., 2016; Levine et al., 2016; Redman et al., 2019; Skurnik et al., 2017). Case control studies can have selection bias since participants are selected based on certain characteristics, which may limit generalizability. Selection bias occurs when the target population does not represent the whole population (Bigelow et al., 2014; Hirshberg et al., 2016; Redman et al., 2019; Skurnik et al., 2017). Some studies in the literature review may have experienced sampling bias since information was gathered from one hospital (Polit & Beck, 2017). In addition, some of the demographic information was missing from those studies that used medical records and hospital databases to extract patient information (Bigelow et al., 2014; Clapp et al., 2016; Johnson et al., 2019; Wagner et al., 2019).

Some of the studies were cross sectional taken from low-income areas and from one site, which may have decreased the generalizability of the findings (Suplee et al., 2017). Another limitation was related to the actual time of data collection as some data were gathered during the

initial hospitalization which failed to address the issue of decreasing readmissions (Aziz et al., 2020). Some studies relied on self-reporting by participants, which may have led to biased answers. Self-reporting in research studies can result in embellished statements and responses made by participants (Polit & Beck, 2017).

Conclusion

Postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia is associated with modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors (Bigelow et al., 2014; Perdiago et al., 2020; Redman et al., 2019; Skurnik et al., 2017; Vilchez et al., 2016). Education about risk factors and clinical presentation of postpartum/hypertension preeclampsia is necessary so patients understand when they need to seek immediate medical help. Patient education should be presented in a simple understandable language using effective teaching methods such as teach- back. Based on this literature review, postpartum education, and discharge instructions at the facility of this project must be revised. Patient follow-up should be planned, especially regarding BP check-ups that may identify small changes significant to prevent complication of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. Nurses need to be cognizant of the importance of close monitoring and communication with postpartum patients through technology, such as text messaging to monitor BP and other clinical presentation, during follow-up appointments after discharge. Nurses are responsible for effective patient education during hospitalization and upon discharge; therefore, they need to employ effective methods of teaching to maximize patient health outcomes.

Methods

The purpose of this QI project was to develop, implement and evaluate a nurse education program related to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia using the guide of the new JC perinatal standard. The aim of this project was to examine changes in nurses' knowledge about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia and self-efficacy regarding the use of evidence-based practices, the new JC perinatal standard, after the completion of an educational intervention. This project also aimed to assess readmission rates before and after implementing the educational intervention, to identify the extent to which patients would receive postpartum education after the completion of the educational intervention and to develop an education protocol that follows the new JC perinatal standard. In this section, I will discuss the project design, setting, sample, protection of human subjects, tools and measures used to collect data, implementation of the project and data analysis and evaluation of the outcomes and the proposed educational program.

Design

This QI project employed a single-group pretest-posttest design. Postpartum nurses were recruited to receive the educational program of the project regarding postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. Single group designs involve the use of a group of participants who receive an intervention; this group is evaluated before and after the intervention is received (Marsden & Torgerson, 2012). Participants are not randomly assigned to a group since there is only one group who is receiving the intervention (Marsden & Torgerson, 2012). This design allows for accurately measuring knowledge before and after the intervention takes place to determine changes in knowledge and self-efficacy (Marsden & Torgerson, 2012). A disadvantage to the single group design is the limited generalizability of the results since only one group is being utilized in the project (Marsden & Torgerson, 2012).

Another limitation of the design is threat to internal validity since one cannot infer that the outcomes, changes in knowledge and self-efficacy of nurses and readmission rates, are a result of the occurrence of the independent variable, which is the education in this project (Knapp, 2016; Polit & Beck, 2017; Spurlock, 2018). The outcome may be affected by participants' knowledge of the content in the pretest questionnaire. Additionally, instrumentation may cause biases if participants become bored anytime during the study causing them to aimlessly answer the questions in the posttest (Polit & Beck, 2017).

Setting

This QI project was implemented at a hospital located in Los Angeles, California. The hospital is public and for non-profit and has 151 beds. The hospital has an ED, one urgent care, two medical surgical units, one telemetry unit, an intensive care unit, one labor and delivery unit, one neonatal intensive care unit, and one postpartum unit. The project took place in the postpartum unit, which has 18 single beds for patients who recently delivered a newborn. Other patients may also get admitted this unit including those who are currently pregnant and in need for additional monitoring for high-risk pregnancy conditions, those who experience a fetal demise, and those who are giving their child up for adoption (Kaiser Permanente, 2020). Approximately 150–200 patients get admitted every month on to the unit.

An average of eight patients need the new postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia education on a daily basis. Patients range from 17–45 years of age, with the majority being African American and Hispanic. This postpartum unit has a large nursery in which the educational intervention of the project was conducted because the nursery is large and can accommodate 27 nurses. It was currently not in use by mothers or babies as they stayed in their individual rooms.

Participants

The unit is composed of 37 registered nurses (RN), four certified nurse assistants (CNA), four ward clerks, three lactation consultants, a nurse educator, an assistant manager, a manager, and a director. Convenience sampling was used to recruit participants in this project. The inclusion criteria were all the RNs that worked directly with postpartum patients on any of the two shifts, 7AM-7PM or 7PM-7AM. The RNs on the unit were female, range from 21 to 65 years of age, with varying years of experience and levels of education from associate degree to master's degree in nursing. Nurses of the unit, including the educator, assistant manager, manager, and director, have diverse cultural backgrounds, with the majority being of Asian race (n=16). Other races include African American (n=4), Hispanic (n=1), Caucasian (n=4), Indian (n=1), and Persian (n=1). The goal of this project was to recruit at least 30 participants.

Ethical Consideration

The project was submitted to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at California State University, Fullerton and the project hospital for approval. The postpartum director provided a letter of support to conduct the project in the postpartum unit. The project caused no harm to the RNs since it involved a non-invasive educational intervention. Participation in the project was voluntary, and participants signed a consent form, which educated participants about the project and its purposes, and reaffirmed that they could withdraw from participation at any time without risks to them or penalty and that they could choose not to answer any of the questions of the project survey. Participants were made aware that identifying data, such as names, would not be collected, their responses would be kept confidential, and the results of the project would be reported collectively.

The project data was stored on a password-protected laptop kept in my home office. Signed consent forms were stored in a locked cabinet in a locked office. To compensate participants for their time, a \$5 Starbucks gift card was offered to each participant.

Data Collection

Data collection was conducted using the project survey that was conducted at baseline before conducting the educational intervention and after the completion of the intervention. The project survey included the Postpartum Nursing Knowledge and Teaching (PNKT) Survey, which has participants' demographics, and the Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self-Efficacy (EBPSE) Scale. After conducting the education, data were collected about whether the patient has received postpartum education during admission and upon discharge from their nurses. Additional data were collected regarding readmission rates before and after conducting the education.

Postpartum Nursing Knowledge and Teaching Survey

The PNKT survey was created by Dr. Patricia Suplee and a team at Rutgers College in 2015 (Suplee et al., 2017). The purpose of the PNKT Survey is to highlight the knowledge of nurses about postpartum care and maternal morbidity and mortality to discover any knowledge gaps (Suplee et al., 2017). It is self-reported and assesses participants' past and present behaviors. The survey consists of participants' demographics, four items about maternal mortality and morbidity knowledge, and 13 items about maternal mortality and morbidity teaching.

Demographics focus on personal attributes of participants, including age, level of nursing education, nursing certification and years of practicing postpartum nursing, in addition to the number of births the hospital reports per year, and the participant's total rate of cesarean section

per year. Maternal mortality and morbidity knowledge examines participants' perceptions about knowledge such as the number of women who die from pregnancy each year, the percentage of deaths that occur during the postpartum period, and the top three leading causes of maternal mortality in the US. Maternal mortality and morbidity teaching investigates patient teaching practices that the nurses perform while on duty and measures the number of times nurses provide information to patients about maternal mortality and morbidity. It also addresses how nurses approach the concept of teaching and providing information to pregnant and postpartum women about complications that might arise before or after discharge.

Reliability coefficient was not tested for this survey. This test ranges from 0–1 and measures the reliability of the instrument (Polit & Beck, 2017). However, the content validity was explained and found that there were gaps in knowledge of nurses on maternal mortality and in delivery of consistent education to all postpartum women about potential postpartum complications (Suplee et al., 2017). Content validity refers to how well a test measures a behavior (Grove & Gray, 2019).

This survey was developed in 2015; therefore, some of its items require updating to follow the new JC perinatal standard. These items included awareness of the new perinatal JC standard, risk factors of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, signs and symptoms of postpartum preeclampsia, the rate of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, the death rate of new mothers due to postpartum complications, and the percentage of the total maternal deaths in the postpartum period.

Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self-Efficacy Scale

The purpose of the EBPSE Scale is to assess nurses' confidence with evidence-based practices; it is self-reported and assists in measuring confidence to avoid undesired behaviors in

different situations (Tucker et al., 2009). The scale was developed by Tucker et al. in 2009; it includes 17 items that assist nurses in processing the scale information and developing basic evidence-based skills. Tucker et al. asserted that the ability to exercise control over work enables nurses to mobilize resources, motivate themselves, and achieve the desired performance; thus, the scale enables nursing professionals to develop EBP skills and evaluates the effectiveness of implementing those skills. Practice evaluation enables nurses to determine when to implement changes to achieve healthcare goals (Tucker et al., 2009).

The items of the scale are not redundant, making it useful in conducting a healthcare self-efficacy test. It was utilized in various studies to assess nurse's knowledge regarding depression and cardiac conditions (Tucker et al., 2009). It is a valuable tool to mentor the nursing staff (Tucker et al., 2009). Mayo Clinic used this scale to conduct personal assessments to measure nurses' leadership roles in education, informatics, and management (Tucker et al., 2009).

The self-efficacy scale uses a rating scale that ranges from 0% as being not confident to 100% as being very confident. Higher scores reflect greater self-efficacy and confidence. The reliability coefficients for the scale ranged from .95 to .98 ($p < .01$), indicating excellent internal consistency (Tucker et al., 2009). The self-efficacy scale was tested for validity and found that it generated accurate confidence measures. Construct validity was established through comparing scores generated by two different cohorts from Mayo Clinic; the average scores of the two cohorts were consistent. Average scores increased significantly ($p < .01$) from time one to time two and time two to time three in cohort one at p value of less than .01, the smaller the p -value, the stronger the evidence (Polit & Beck, 2017).

Procedure

After obtaining the IRB approval from California State University, Fullerton and the project hospital, flyers were distributed on the postpartum unit to educate nurses about the QI project and its purposes and ask them to participate. See Appendix J. The flyer discussed eligibility and exclusion criteria. The project and the opportunity to volunteer were also discussed in the nurses' morning and evening huddles. Nurses were instructed to contact the project author with any questions or concerns about the project.

Eligible volunteers were instructed to sign a written consent form after all their questions were addressed. Participants completed the project paper survey at baseline before the implementation of the educational intervention to collect data about their demographics and knowledge and self-efficacy related to postpartum care and adopting the new JC perinatal standard. The recruitment process continued for two weeks with a goal to obtain at least 30 participants.

Conducting the education began immediately after baseline and pre-intervention data collection was completed. Eight educational sessions during March 2020 were conducted and the sessions included teaching all the unit RNs; those sessions were conducted in the nursery on the day and the night shifts. Each session took approximately 45 minutes. Fifteen minutes were assigned at the end of the educational session to review and answer questions.

Despite this fact that education included all the RNs, participation in the project was voluntary. A PowerPoint presentation and an education pamphlet were used during the education session. After the education was received, nurses who attended the session completed the post-intervention survey including the PNKT survey and the EBPSE scale.

Educational Intervention

The educational content was obtained from the California Maternal Quality Care Collaborative (CMQCC, 2013) and the Preeclampsia Foundation. The Preeclampsia Foundation (2020) aims to educate health care providers, patients, and the public how life-threatening preeclampsia is. The CMQCC uses research, quality improvement toolkits, state-wide outreach collaborative, and its innovative Maternal Data Center to improve health outcomes for mothers and infants (CMQCC, 2013). It also often collaborates with the ACOG to seek current research (CMQCC, 2013). The ACOG (2020) is a professional association composed of medical doctors who specialize in obstetrics and gynecology in the U.S.

A discussion supported by a PowerPoint presentation and the education pamphlet from the Preeclampsia Foundation were utilized to teach nurses about the new JC perinatal standard and its significance, with emphasis on postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, the importance of educating postpartum patients and what their patients must be educated about. The nurse education discussed sign and symptoms, risk factors, and how the disease may clinically present itself in relation to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, so they are able to educate patients confidently about those topics. Nurses were also asked to demonstrate how to apply the accurate size BP. Additionally, they were made aware that they need to teach patients how to measure their own BP and when to seek medical care after discharge. Nurses educated patients in increments during every shift during admission and upon discharge to ensure that the patient had a solid understanding and to prevent the burden of information overload. I visually checked and assessed each nurse performing patient education via in person observation of teaching information about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia by practicing with each other.

The preeclampsia education pamphlet was used to further educate nurses about disease management of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. Since it can happen to any woman who up to twelve weeks after giving birth, it was important to teach all postpartum patients. The risks of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia may be seizures, stroke, organ failure, and death. It is related to elevated BP, and the sign of this may occur in severe headaches. All postpartum patients should be stringently taught that the warning signs include nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, headaches, visual changes, (seeing black spots), and swelling of the hands and feet (Preeclampsia Foundation, 2020). It is imperative for the nurse to educate the patient on keeping follow up appointments and seeking emergency assistance if any of these symptoms occur (Preeclampsia Foundation, 2020).

Timeline of the QI Project

December 18, 2020, Defense Proposal

January 19-31, 2020, Student Onboard Process at the Hospital

February 1-28, 2021, Pending IRB Approval from both facilities

February 1-28, 2021, Pending IRB Approval from both facilities

March 1-15, 2021, IRB Approval, Data Collection, Nurse Recruitment

March 20-31, 2021, Data Collection, Nurse Data Analysis, Results and Discussion

Data Analysis

This project utilized QI Macros and Intellectus Statistics to measure the changes in nursing knowledge related to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. The measures included the PNKT survey, EBPSE scale, assessing whether there was an increase in readmissions and if the nurses were educating the patients with the new material. The analysis included both static and dynamic statistics including the use of run charts and control charts and paired sample *t*-tests

to measure the changes in knowledge and self-efficacy before and after implementation of the education.

Table 1

Evaluation and Measurement of Outcomes

Outcome	Operation definition	Method of measurement	Analysis
Knowledge related to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia	Pre and post surveys on knowledge related to postpartum complications	PNKT survey	Paired samples T-test to compare the pre- and post-survey data
Self-efficacy related to evidence-based-practice	Pre and post surveys on self-efficacy	Evidence based nursing practice self-efficacy scale	Paired samples T-test compare the pre- and post-survey data
Assessing readmission rates	The number of postpartum patients readmitted after discharge	Postpartum readmission book and inpatient database	Run charts then I chart

Run charts are also called run sequence plots (Provost & Murray, 2011). They are used to show data in a proper time sequence (Provost & Murray, 2011). Run charts are used when there are not enough data points to create a control chart (Langley et al., 2009). Run charts show patterns that are present in the process and have a median line. Run charts are easier to construct and are straightforward. They show if there are losses or profits after change process has been implanted (Langley et al., 2009). Run charts do not help to explain the reason for upward or downward trends. Run charts do not show the lower control limits or the upper control limits. Run charts were used in this project to show a visual analysis of the changes in hospital readmissions before and after nurses receive the education, and whether nurses are performing patient education for eligible patients prior to discharge.

Control charts are also a graphical representation that are used to show variations in a variable, which may be the result of a common cause or a special cause (Provost & Murray,

2011). Unlike the run charts, control charts have a center line and an upper and lower limit. Special causes are those that are not a part of the system (process or product) or do not affect everyone but arise because of specific circumstances (Langley et al., 2009). The special cause can only be effectively determined through the five rules:

Types of Control Charts

There are different types of charts for different types of data. Data are described as attribute or variables data. An attribute is a product characteristic that has a discrete value and can be counted (Provost & Murray, 2011). A percent defective known as a P chart is appropriate to use when categorical data is used in two classes or parts (Provost & Murray, 2011). A P chart is a control chart used to observe the fraction of defectives initiated by a process (Provost & Murray, 2011). P charts are appropriate when both the number of defectives measured, and the size of the total sample can be counted (Provost & Murray, 2011). A proportion can then be computed and used as the statistics of measurement. For example, what is high and what is low.

A C chart is a control chart used to watch and count the number of defects per unit (Provost & Murray, 2011). A C chart measures attributes of data to identify common or special causes (Provost & Murray, 2011). It applies to the number of nonconformities in sample of constant size. The control limit of this chart is based on Poisson distribution (Provost & Murray, 2011). Poisson distribution helped to represent the number of hospital readmissions two months before and after.

A T chart was used to plot hospital postpartum readmissions. T charts are used when the variable of interest (in this case readmissions) is relatively rare. The T chart provides a representation of the measurement of time between each occurrence (Provost & Murray, 2011). In this project, the baseline data were the time between postpartum readmissions. Readmission

data was requested from the information technology department. A readmission was defined as any patient who was readmitted one and two months after the nurses received the education. The information contained the patient ID number, date of delivery, date of readmission, and readmission reason. Patients readmitted within 42 days of deliver with a primary reason for readmission of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia were included in the sample. The exclusion criteria were patients readmitted after 42 days or patients admitted for reasons other than postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. The dates of readmission and the days between readmissions were plotted on a T chart to measure the time between each readmission event. The incident of interest was readmissions and the time on/between events. The T chart measures the time between events. For example, if a postpartum readmission occurred on November 15, 20, and 25. The admissions would occur five days apart. The goal was to decrease the number of days between readmissions

Paired sample *t*-tests are statistical processes used to identify if the mean disparity amid two observational sets (Duignan, 2016). In a paired sample *t*-test, each object or subject is measured two times (Duignan, 2016)). Thus, leading to observations and pairs. For this project, paired sample *t*-tests were used to measure the effectiveness of the education intervention. A thorough assessment of the before scores and after scores were calculated to determine the sample mean and sample standard deviation obtained from the pre and post surveys based on a self-report about self-efficacy ratings.

Evaluation Plan

Data regarding education was evaluated to determine whether subgroups were of adequate size. Once the size was determined, either a P chart or C chart was completed. Data for

the participants (nurses) was entered into Microsoft Excel sheet. The QI macros program was used to develop the charts. Run charts were developed first, after 10 data points were collected, the Run chart was converted into Control charts. The data were collected for four weeks adding more data points.

Conclusion

Postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia is a severe condition that mothers may develop after giving birth. Nurses need to be aware and communicate this critical information to their patients. Patient guidance during postpartum care and management must occur to reduce readmission rates due to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. Development and implementation of a nursing education program is critical for successful adaptation of the updated JC perinatal standards that address nurse and patient education.

This QI project assessed postpartum nurses' attitudes and gaps in knowledge regarding postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, which was foundational to build an effective nursing educational intervention. This educational intervention helped nurses to provide safe and high-quality care. The intervention also assessed some of the relevant nursing skills that are essential to handle postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia properly and to teach about it with confidence.

Results

This section describes results found in this QI project, which were based on the four aims. The aims were to (a) examine changes in nurses' knowledge about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia and nurse self-efficacy regarding the use of evidence-based practices, and their knowledge of the new JC perinatal standards after the completion of an educational intervention; (b) assess readmission rates before and after implementation of the educational intervention; (c) identify the extent to which patients received the postpartum education after nurse completion of the educational intervention; and (d) develop an education protocol based on new JC perinatal standard. After the data were collected, they were analyzed using descriptive statistics and control charts using QI Macros® and Intellectus Statistics™. Demographic information on the nurse's characteristics were also described.

Population and Facility Demographic Characteristics

The demographic characteristics of the population of nurses who participated in the project were assessed. A total of 27 nurses participated in the QI project, whose ages ranged from 31–64. There were 29% (8) nurses between the ages of 31–40, 51% (14) of the nurses were between the ages of 41–50, 11% (3) of the nurses were between the ages of 51–60, and 7% (2) of the nurses were greater than 61 years of age. There were no nurses below the age of 30.

Most of the nurses who participated in the project held advanced degrees. Of the 27 nurses, 85% (23) of them held a bachelor's degree in nursing, 11% (3) held a master's degree in nursing, 3% (1) nurse held a degree not listed. Of the 100% (27) of nurses all had various maternal certifications. The nurses who participated in the project had more than 20 years of experience working in the postpartum unit. Of the nurses, 7% (2) nurses practiced as a postpartum nurse for three to five years, 22% (6) nurses had practiced six to 10 years as a

postpartum nurse, 51% (14) nurses had practiced 11-20 years as a postpartum nurse, and 18% (5) had practiced more than 20 years as a postpartum nurse.

Nurse awareness regarding the new JC perinatal standards was assessed pre and post the educational intervention. Of the nurses, 33% (9) were not aware of the new JC perinatal standards, and 66% (18) were aware of the new JC perinatal standards. When the nurses were asked what the new standards were 70% (19) answered correctly that it was postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia and hemorrhage; however, 30% (8) answered incorrectly by only listing hemorrhage as the standard. The nurses were asked to determine the number of births the hospital has each year and 51% (14) stated more than 1,000, which was the correct answer. Table 2 provides information on the sociodemographic characteristics of the nurses included in this project.

Table 2*Sample Demographics*

Characteristics	n	%
Age		
20–30	0	0
31–40	8	29.62
41–50	14	51.85
51–60	3	11.11
>61	2	7.4
Highest level of education		
Diploma	0	0
Associates degree	0	0
Baccalaureate degree	23	85.19
Master’s degree	3	11.11
DNP	0	0
PhD	0	0
Other		3.7
Certifications		
RNC-MNN	2	7.4
RNC-OB	0	0
CLEC	10	37.03
IBCLC	0	0
Other	1	3.7
None of the above	14	51.85
Years practicing as a postpartum nurse		
Less than one year	0	0
1-2 years	0	0
3-5 years	2	7.4
6-10 years	6	22.22
11-20 years	14	51.85
Greater than 20 years	5	18.51
State of Employment		
States employed, CA	27	100
Are you aware of the new JC perinatal standards?		
No	9	33.33
Yes	18	66.66

Postpartum Knowledge Teaching Survey

The knowledge of postpartum morbidity and mortality for the nurses was evaluated based on the survey responses as seen in Table 3. Questions 1–9 were questions pertaining to the population and facility demographics and can be seen in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 3*Facility Demographics*

What are the new standards?	n	%
Postpartum infection	0	0
Postpartum hemorrhage	8	29.63
Infection sepsis	0	0
Postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia and hemorrhage	19	70.37
How many births does your hospital report a year?		
<1000	3	11.11
1001–3000	14	51.85
3001–5000	3	11.11
>5001	0	0
Not sure	7	25.92
What is your total cesarean rate per year?		
<20%	0	0
21-30%	11	40.74
31-40%	6	22.22
41-50%	0	0
>51%	0	0
Not sure	10	37.03

Pre and posttest responses were analyzed for questions 10–13, which assessed nurses' knowledge of maternal morbidity and mortality. Question 10, asked how many women in the U.S. die each year from pregnancy related complications. There were 22% (6) of the nurses who answered correctly before the educational intervention. After the educational intervention, 100% (27) of the nurses answered correctly (See Figure 2).

Figure 2

Question 10: Pre and Post Nurse Awareness of the Number of Deaths Each Year From Pregnancy Complications

Question 11 asked, what percentage of the total number of maternal deaths takes place during the postpartum period. There were 29% (8) of nurses who answered correctly pre-educational intervention. After the educational intervention, 70% (19) of the nurses answered correctly (See Figure 3).

Figure 3

Question 11: Pre and Post Nurse Awareness of the Percentage of Maternal Deaths that Occurred During Postpartum

Question 12 asked the nurses to rank the top three leading causes of maternal mortality in the United States, before the educational intervention, 18% (5) of nurses answered correctly. After the educational intervention, 92% (25) nurses answered correctly (Figure 4).

Figure 4

Question 12: Pre and Post Awareness of the Top Three Causes of Maternal Mortality in the United States

Question 13 asked the nurses if maternal morbidity has increased, decreased, or stayed the same over the last decade. Prior to the educational intervention 76% (19) of the nurses answered correctly (See Figure 5). After the educational intervention, 100% (27) of the nurses answered correctly.

Figure 5

Question 13: Pre and Post Nurse Awareness of the Maternal Morbidity from the Last Decade

Questions 14–25 discussed the nurses’ awareness of education that patients receive in the postpartum unit. Question 14 asked the nurses when was the majority of postpartum discharge education was provided to women on your unit. Prior to the educational intervention, 14% (4) nurses answered they would provide the majority of discharge education on the first day of admission, 74% (20) of the nurses indicated they would provide the majority of discharge education throughout the patient’s stay, and 11% (3) of the nurses answered they would provide the majority of discharge education on the day of discharge. After the educational intervention 7% (2) of nurses answered the majority of discharge teaching should be taught on the first day of admission, 92% (25) of nurses answered throughout the stay, and no nurses answered on the day of discharge (See Figure 6).

Figure 6

Question 14: Pre and Post Assessment of the Day Postpartum Discharge Education is Provided

Question 15 asked the nurses on the day of discharge, specifically, how much time does a nurse spend reinforcing all postpartum discharge information with women. There were 55% (15) of nurses who answered 31-40 minutes pre and post educational intervention (See Figure 7).

Figure 7

Day of Discharge: Pre and Post Time Spent Reinforcing Discharge Information

Question 16 asked if it was the nurses' responsibility to educate all women. There were 74% (20) and 88% (24) pre and post educational interventional who said it was the responsibility of the nurses to educate all women (See Figure 8).

Figure 8

Pre and Post Assessment of Belief that Nurses are Responsible for Educating Women

Question 17 asked how much time a nurse spends teaching about warning signs of potential complications. The nurses' answers varied with 77% (21) nurses answering that it takes six to 20 minutes (See Figure 9).

Figure 9

Nurses' Time Spent Teaching About Warning Signs for Potential Complications

Question 18 asked how likely the nurses would discuss the following complications with all women. Some of the complications included hypertension, hemorrhage, infection, venous thrombosis embolism, pulmonary embolism, postpartum depression, preeclampsia, and cardiac events. Most nurses indicated they would discuss the postpartum complications with women. However, after the educational intervention, all the nurses believed they would discuss the following complications except pulmonary embolism and preeclampsia (See Figure 10).

Figure 10*Likelihood of Discussing Complications with Women*

Question 19 asked how likely the nurse would discuss the following potential signs and symptoms of complications with ALL postpartum women prior to discharge. Some of the complications included severe constant headaches, vision changes, swelling of hands and feet, weight gain, elevated BP, seizures, difficulty breathing, chest pain, thoughts of hurting baby or self, feeling depressed, bleeding saturating one or more pads per hour, passing clots larger than an egg, nausea, and dizziness, swelling of one leg, redness or warmth of calf, pain in calf area, temperature greater than 100.4 degrees, and bad smelling of discharge. All of the nurses indicated they would discuss the postpartum complications with women. However, after the educational intervention all the nurses indicated that they would discuss the following complications except seizures 96% (26) (See Figure 11).

Figure 11

Likelihood of Discussing Signs and Symptoms of Complications with Women Prior to Discharge

Question 20 asked how competent the nurses felt discussing these topics with all women prior to discharge. Some of the topics included hemorrhage, hypertension, infection, deep vein thrombosis, pulmonary embolism, postpartum depression, preeclampsia/eclampsia, and cardiac events. After the educational intervention, 100% (27) of nurses indicated they were competent with the topics of hemorrhage, hypertension, infection, and preeclampsia and 96% (26) of the nurses indicated they were competent in discussing topics of postpartum depression and deep vein thrombosis. However, 92% (25) nurses indicated they were less competent with the topics regarding pulmonary embolism and cardiac events (See Figure 12).

Figure 12

Feelings of Competence Discussing Postpartum Topics with Women Prior to Discharge

Question 21 asked the nurses how helpful it would be to have a one-page educational handout about warning signs. There were 88% (24) of nurses who answered it would be very helpful pre and post educational intervention and 11% (3) of the nurses felt it would be helpful (See Figure 13).

Figure 13

Helpfulness of a One Page Educational Handout of Warning Signs

Question 22 asked the nurses how they documented postpartum education, 51% (14) and 55% (15) of the nurses pre and post intervention answered they documented through the use of computer charting (See Figure 14).

Figure 14

Documentation of Postpartum Education

Question 23 asked the nurses how likely would they use the following resources to increase their knowledge about postpartum morbidity and mortality? One hundred percent of the nurses answered they would use online education to increase their knowledge about postpartum morbidity and mortality (See Figure 15).

Figure 15

Use of Resources to Increase Knowledge Regarding Postpartum Mortality and Morbidity

Question 24 asked how the nurses stayed current with the evidence-based practices in maternal/infant care and 81% (22) of the nurses answered that they take online courses to help themselves stay current pre-educational intervention and post educational intervention (See Figure 16).

Figure 16

Methods Identified by Participants for Staying Up to Date on Evidence-Based Practices

Question 25 asked the nurses if they thought there was a relationship between the postpartum education they provided women prior to them being discharged from the hospital and postpartum maternal mortality and morbidity. All nurses 96% (26) except one responded that there was a relationship between maternal mortality, morbidity, and discharge teaching (See Figure 17).

Figure 17

Awareness of the Relationship between Mortality, Morbidity, and Postpartum Education

Evidence-Based Self Efficacy Scale

The EBPSE was used to determine how the nurses felt about evidence-based practices and their ability to apply them to their everyday practice. The scale included 17 items related to evidence-based nursing. This tool used a zero to 100% response scale, with higher scores indicating greater self-efficacy. Question one asked the nurses if they routinely asked themselves questions about their practice. Question two asked the nurses if they were able to locate resources in their department and institution to facilitate their understanding of research literature relevant to their nursing practice. Question three asked if the nurses were able to locate resources in their department and institution to help them facilitate an evidence-based practice change. The Intellectus Statistics™ is a computer software program used to analyze the results of the EBPSE scale. Aggregate scores for all questions were combined from the pre-test period resulting in a

mean score of 73.51 and aggregate post-test responses resulted in a mean of 84.44, with a p -value of $<.001$, indicating there was statistically significant overall improvement in the use of evidence-based practices after the educational intervention (See Figure 18).

Figure 18

Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self-Efficacy Scale: A Measure of Confidence

Readmission Rates

Readmission included any postpartum patient who delivered in the prior 30 days and was readmitted to the hospital for postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia. The specific date of readmission was recorded sequentially for the calendar year beginning January 2020 to March 2021. The data was analyzed using the computer program called QI macros® and was displayed as a T-chart. The T-chart is a control chart that is used to measure the time in between events, in this case readmissions. The number of days between the readmissions was the focus of the chart. There were 47 data points, which represented the actual readmission dates. There was only one data point after the training started. The T-chart showed that a woman was being readmitted to the project facility with the diagnosis of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia every 7.29 days on average. The goal was to increase the number of days between readmissions. Even though

one readmission occurred after the educational intervention, more time was needed to see if the educational intervention affected the readmissions in the long term. The T-chart showed common cause variation (See Figure 19). Common cause variation is normal variation that is built into the system and affects the whole system (Langley et al., 2009). This indicated that the educational intervention did not result in a change in the number of days between readmissions. Additional data were needed to identify a special cause variation, which may have resulted from the educational intervention. Langley described special causes as those that are not a part of the system and can arise because of specific circumstances/intervention (Langley et al., 2009).

Figure 19

T-Chart

Conclusion

I employed a pre-test-post-test design in this QI project. The results obtained from the PKNT survey showed an increase in scores after the educational intervention. The results obtained in the EBPSE also showed an increase after the educational intervention. The results of the two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(26) = -5.56$, $p < .001$, indicating the null hypothesis can be rejected. This finding suggests the difference in the mean of the pre EBPSE scale and the mean of the post EBPSE scale was significantly different from zero (Intellectus, 2021). The results showed using the T-chart that there was one readmission after the educational intervention.

DISCUSSION

Postpartum nurses can reduce readmission rates by implementing evidence-based practices and interventions (Suplee et al., 2017). This QI project illustrated the development and implementation of an education program to decrease postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia readmissions and improve patient outcomes. The education program provided the nurses with an opportunity to learn about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, evidence-based practices, and the new JC perinatal standards.

Sociodemographic Data

The demographic characteristics of the participants in the QI project included their age, level of education, years as a postpartum nurse, and certifications held. Over half of the postpartum nurses were between the ages of 41–50. Most of the nurses held a bachelor's degree in nursing. More than half of the nurses had 11–20 years of experience as a postpartum nurse. More than half of them did not have any maternity certifications.

The sociodemographic characteristics of participants in this project were consistent with the findings in the literature. The literature showed that postpartum nurses were female, mostly held bachelor's degree were older age between 41–60 (Lewis, 2020; Reid et al., 2018; Suplee et al., 2017). The literature identified older age, increased years of experience and being married were associated with an increase in efficacy in teaching patients among postpartum nurses (Reid et al., 2018). Perhaps nurses who were older and had more experience felt more comfortable and confident teaching postpartum patients.

Postpartum Knowledge

In this QI project, the results revealed that participants had an increase in the overall knowledge scores after completing the education intervention. Nurses should have sufficient

knowledge to teach a postpartum patient about possible complications that can occur after giving birth. This is imperative to prevent death and reduce postpartum readmissions (Suplee et al., 2017).

After completing the educational interventions, an increase in knowledge among postpartum nurses was found in the following areas:(a) pregnancy complications, (b) maternal deaths in the postpartum period, (c) the top three causes of maternal mortality, (d) the new JC perinatal standards, (e) maternal morbidity and mortality awareness, (f) the number of deaths from pregnancy complications, (g) the percentage of maternal deaths during the postpartum period, (h) the top three leading causes maternal mortality in the United States, and maternal morbidity from the last decade. This increase in knowledge is consistent with the previous literature (Lewis, 2020; Suplee et al., 2016, Van Houwelingen et al., 2021). Through education, the nurses may have achieved a better understanding of postpartum complications, which was reflected in the increase of their postpartum knowledge (Lewis, 2020). The bulk of nurses were not up to date with morbidity and mortality. The research supports that an education program is beneficial to the staff and was shown to have positive benefits (Lewis, 2020; Van Houwelingen et al., 2021). Utilizing an education program may improve the postpartum nurses' knowledge as well as ensuring that all postpartum patients would be educated with the same information. Suplee et al. (2016) conducted a study and found that postpartum nurses were inconsistent with their postpartum teaching to patients. According to Van Houwelingen (2021), nurses who received a two-day training reported an increase in knowledge and self-efficacy in telehealth.

Self-Efficacy

After the completing of the educational intervention, there was a significant increase in self-efficacy related to evidence-based practice and the implementation of the new JC perinatal

standard. The educational intervention may have helped participants to achieve a better understanding using evidence in their nursing practice, which was reflected in the increase of their self-efficacy. It was indicated that education increased self-efficacy (O’Leary et al., 2016; Van Houwelingen et al., 2021).

Similar to these findings, nurses reported an increase in knowledge and self-efficacy in providing patients care after receiving training in their specific areas of practice (O’Leary et al., 2016; Van Houwelingen et al., 2021). According to Van Houwelingen, nurses who received a two-day training reported an increase in self-efficacy in telehealth. O’Leary et al. found that nurses who received standard education and simulation reported an increase in assessing pediatric deterioration.

Readmission Rates

I found that the number of readmissions due to postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia was decreased after the completion of the educational intervention. Postpartum hospital readmissions rates have increased in the last 10 years (Clapp et al., 2016; Mogos et al., 2018). The educational intervention focused on the signs and symptoms of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, the risk factors of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, the new perinatal JC standards and determining the appropriate BP cuff size. After providing the nursing education, only one readmission occurred within 12 days. This decrease in readmission may be attributed to focusing on educating patients throughout hospitalization and upon discharge. Therefore, patients may have notified the health care provider about any symptoms or complications in a timely manner before the condition worsened. Before the completion of the educational intervention, nurses taught their patients only upon discharge. Additionally, the nursing education may have led to another change in practice since the unit nurses provided

postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia education only to those patients who were diagnosed with preeclampsia during their pregnancy which did not comply with the JC new perinatal standard (Kaiser Permanente, 2020). However, after the completion of the intervention, nurses provided education to all postpartum patients, which may have attributed to reduce readmissions.

Polster (2015) indicated that if discharge teaching is consistent among all medical surgical patients, that would reduce readmissions. Also, Healy et al. (2013) found that patients who participated in an inpatient diabetes education program had a reduction in patient readmissions. Education about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia can potentially prevent readmissions (Morley & Levin, 2021).

Strengths and Limitations

The QI project utilized a pre-test and post-test design that successfully addressed the purpose and aims of the project. A benefit of using this design is that one can determine how much of a change occurred and make a comparison (Polit & Beck 2017). The project utilized QI Macros®. QI Macros analyzed the readmission data and created a visual control chart that described and plotted the data (Provost & Murray, 2011).

The project was able to successfully recruit 27 participants without attrition. The project developed and utilized an evidence-based education program, which has been adopted by the project facility and used during new nursing orientation and annually during critical events training. The education program was well received by the nurses in the project facility. It additionally, provided a standardized method to educate nurses about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia to empower them to educate patients and enhance safety.

There were several limitations to the project. The project was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic, which delayed the IRB approval, causing the project to be implemented

over a four-week period, rather than the intended eight weeks. Changes in leadership caused more delays since the new leadership required the project be conducted at another facility. The new implementation site required extensive efforts to educate the hospital management and the postpartum unit about the project and its purposes.

The project employed a small sample size of 27 nurses which limits generalizability of the results. The sample may not represent the population of the postpartum nurses because the QI project was conducted in one metropolitan hospital (Polit & Beck, 2017). To increase generalizability, larger samples in more hospitals should be used (Grove & Gray, 2019).

Future Clinical Implications

Nurses should educate all postpartum patients on postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia as it is a major complication that can result in death (Suplee et al., 2017). The education program helped increase the postpartum nurses' knowledge by discussing postpartum complications such as postpartum hypertension preeclampsia, use of a BP cuff and evidence-based practices (Suplee et al., 2017). Clinical implications include implementing a standardized nurse education program, adhering to the JC perinatal standards to improve patient quality of care, decreasing time between readmission with the diagnosis of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, and reducing maternal morbidity and mortality. These future implications will be a model for other health care organizations and increase the knowledge base of postpartum nurses. The future implications will also bring awareness to postpartum nurses about the importance of severe postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia and how the lack of standardized nursing intervention and evidence-based practices causes nurses to not be consistent with their teaching plans. The findings in the project supported the new JC perinatal standard; therefore, policies and protocols should be developed in adherence to the JC updated perinatal standards to improve patient

quality of care. This can be done by ensuring that all new postpartum nurses complete the nursing education program during orientation, and it should be included in the critical events annual training.

Conclusion

In conclusion, postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia is a serious illness that may occur up to 12 weeks of delivery (Katsi et al., 2020; Powles & Gandhi, 2017). Nurses need to be cognizant of this condition. Postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia has been associated with seizures, strokes, disability, hospital readmissions, and death (Al Safi et al., 2011; Katsi et al., 2020; Sharma & Kilpatrick, 2017; Suplee et al. 2017; Sutton et al., 2018). Educating nurses will help them educate the patients in a consistent and standardized manner to prevent/reduce maternal morbidity and mortality in this population. The Iowa Model was in alignment with this QI project in that the Iowa Model guided the project and was useful in managing an evidence-based practice change to implement a new practice in the postpartum unit. The QI project provided the necessary research findings that were able to be translated into clinical practice while improving clinical outcomes for postpartum patients (Brown, 2014). The QI project was useful in providing evidence base education to the postpartum nurses and decreasing postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia readmissions.

References

- Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality. (n.d.). *Readmission rates*.
<https://www.ahrq.gov/data/infographics/readmission-rates.html>
- Al-Safi, Z., Imudia, A. N., Filetti, L. C., Hobson, D. T., Bahado-Singh, R. O., & Awonuga, A. O. (2011). Delayed postpartum Preeclampsia and eclampsia. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 118(5), 1102–1107. <https://doi.org/10.1097/aog.0b013e318231934c>
- American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. (2019). *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 133(1), 1–1. <https://doi.org/10.1097/aog.0000000000003018>
- American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. (2020). *Optimizing postpartum care*. <https://www.acog.org/clinical/clinical-guidance/committee-opinion/articles/2018/05/optimizing-postpartum-care>
- Aseltine, R. H., Yan, J., Fleischman, S., Katz, M., & DeFrancesco, M. (2015). Racial and ethnic disparities in hospital readmissions after delivery. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 126(5), 1040–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1097/aog.0000000000001090>
- Aziz, A., Gyamfi-Bannerman, C., Siddiq, Z., Wright, J., Goffman, D., Sheen, J., D’Alton, M., & Friedman, A. (2020). Maternal outcomes by race during postpartum readmissions. *Obstetric Anesthesia Digest*, 40(1), 1–2.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.aoa.0000652652.53559.6a>
- Banke-Thomas, A., Rosser, C., Brady, R., & Shields, L. (2019). Patient costs and outcomes before and after the institution of a preeclampsia quality improvement initiative in a southwestern tertiary facility. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology*, 39(6), 748–752.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01443615.2019.1575343>

- Bastable, S. B. (2017). *Nurse as educator: Principles of teaching and learning for nursing practice*. Jones & Bartlett Learning.
- Bernstein, P. S., Martin, J. N., Barton, J. R., Shields, L. E., Druzin, M. L., Scavone, B. M., Frost, J., Morton, C. H., Ruhl, C., Slage, J., Tsigas, E. Z., Jaffer, S., & Menard, M. K. (2017). Consensus bundle on severe hypertension during pregnancy and the postpartum period. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 46(5), 776–787.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2017.05.003>
- Bigelow, C. A., Pereira, G. A., Warmesley, A., Cohen, J., Getrajdman, C., Moshier, E., Paris, J., Factor, S. H., Bianco, A., & Stone, J. (2014). Risk factors for new-onset late postpartum preeclampsia in women without a history of preeclampsia. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 210(4), 338-e1.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.aoa.0000463828.01127.0f>
- Boyd, M. M. (2017). Implementing skin-to-skin contact for cesarean birth. *Association of periOperative Registered Nurses Journal*, 105(6), 579–592.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aorn.2017.04.003>
- Brousseau, E. C., Danilack, V., Cai, F., & Matteson, K. (2017). Emergency department visits for postpartum hypertension. *Hypertension in Pregnancy*, 36(2), 212–216.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10641955.2017.1299171>
- Brown, C. G. (2014). The Iowa model of evidence-based practice to promote quality care: An illustrated example in oncology nursing. *Clinical Journal of Oncology Nursing*, 18(2), 157–159. <https://doi.org/10.1188/14.cjon.157-159>
- California Department of Health Care Services. (2020, May 1). *Using California maternity data to drive quality improvement*. www.dhcs.ca.gov/services/calendar/Documents/Main.pdf

- California Department of Public Health. (2018, May 24). *Maternal child and adolescent health division*. <https://www.cdph.ca.gov/Programs/CFH/DMCAH/RPPC/Pages/California-Maternal-Quality-Improvement-Toolkit.aspx>
- California Maternal Quality Care Collaborative. (2013). *Preeclampsia toolkit*. <https://www.cmqcc.org/resources-tool-kits/toolkits/preeclampsia-toolkit>.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2020, September 8). *Severe maternal morbidity*. <https://www.cdc.gov/reproductivehealth/maternalinfanthealth/severematernalmorbidity.html>
- Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services. (2020). *Hospital readmissions reduction program (HRRP)*. <https://www.cms.gov/Medicare/Medicare-Fee-for-Service-Payment/AcuteInpatientPPS/Readmissions-Reduction-Program>
- Clapp, M. A., Little, S. E., Zheng, J., & Robinson, J. N. (2016). A multi-state analysis of postpartum readmissions in the United States. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 215(1), 113.e1–113.e10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2016.01.174>
- Clapp, M. A., Little, S. E., Zheng, J., Robinson, J. N., & Kaimal, A. J. (2018). The relative effects of patient and hospital factors on postpartum readmissions. *Journal of Perinatology*, 38(7), 804–812. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41372-018-0125-8>
- Cohen, J., Vaiman, D., Sibai, B. M., & Haddad, B. (2015). Blood pressure changes during the first stage of labor and for the prediction of early postpartum preeclampsia: A prospective study. *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, 184, 103–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2014.11.020>
- Combs, C. M. (2017). Recognition and management of preeclampsia. *Hospital Medicine Clinics*, 6(3), 348–358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ehmc.2017.04.001>

- Cullen, L., Kleiber, C., Tucker, S., DeBerg, J., & Hanrahan, K. (2018). *Evidence-based practice in action: Comprehensive strategies, tools, and tips from the University of Iowa hospitals and clinics*. Sigma Theta Tau International.
- D'Alton, M. E., Main, E. K., Menard, M. K., & Levy, B. S. (2014). The national partnership for maternal safety. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, *123*(5), 973–977.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/aog.0000000000000219>
- Dhariwal, N. K., & Lynde, G. C. (2017). Update in the Management of patients with preeclampsia. *Anesthesiology Clinics*, *35*(1), 95–106.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anclin.2016.09.009>
- Dickens, C. (2013). Health literacy and nursing. *American Journal of Nursing*, *113*(6), 52–57.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.naj.0000431271.83277.2f>
- D'Oria, Robyn, Myers, John, & Logsdon, M. Cynthia. (2016). Strategies to reduce maternal mortality during the first year after birth. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic and Neonatal Nursing*, *45*(6), 885–893. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2016.04.013>
- Duignan, J. (2016). Paired sample t-test. A dictionary of business research methods. Oxford University Press.
<https://www.oxfordreference.com/view/10.1093/acref/9780191792236.001.0001/acref-9780191792236-e-414?rskey=eoDDmp&result=2>
- Durkee, R. (2020, August 21). *New Joint Commission standards for perinatal care*. Vizient Newsroom. <https://newsroom.vizientinc.com/new-joint-commission-standards-for-perinatal-care-is-your-organization-ready.htm>.

- El-Sayed, A. A. F. (2017). Preeclampsia: A review of the pathogenesis and possible management strategies based on its pathophysiological derangements. *Taiwanese Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 56(5), 593–598. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tjog.2017.08.004>
- Felix, H. C., Seaberg, B., Bursac, Z., Thostenson, J., & Stewart, M. K. (2015). Why do patients keep coming back? Results of a readmitted patient survey. *Social Work in HealthCare*, 54(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00981389.2014.966881>
- Goel, A., Maski, M. R., Bajracharya, S., Wenger, J. B., Zhang, D., Salahuddin, S., Shahul, S. S., Thadhani, R., Seely, E. W., Karumanchi, S. A., & Rana, S. (2015). Epidemiology and mechanisms of De Novo and persistent hypertension in the postpartum period. *Circulation*, 132(18), 1726–1733. <https://doi.org/10.1161/circulationaha.115.015721>
- Gordon, M., Bartruff, L., Gordon, S., Lofgren, M., & Widness, J. A. (2008). How fast is too fast? *Advances in Neonatal Care*, 8(4), 198–207. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.anc.0000333707.37776.08>
- Griffey, R. T., Shin, N., Jones, S., Aginam, N., Gross, M., Kinsella, Y., Williams, J.A., Carpenter, C. R., Goodman, M., & Kaphingst, K. A. (2015). The impact of teach-back on comprehension of discharge instructions and satisfaction among emergency patients with limited health literacy: A randomized, controlled study. *Journal of Communication in Healthcare*, 8, (1), 10-21. <https://doi.org/10.1179/1753807615Y.0000000001>
- Grove, S. K., & Gray, J. R. (2019). *Understanding nursing research building an evidence-based practice* (7th ed). Elsevier.
- Gu, W., Lin, J., Hou, Y.-Y., Lin, N., Song, M.-F., Zeng, W.-J., Shang, J., & Huang, H.-F. (2020). Effects of low-dose aspirin on the prevention of preeclampsia and pregnancy outcomes: A randomized controlled trial from Shanghai, China. *European Journal of Obstetrics &*

Gynecology and Reproductive Biology, 248, 156–163.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2020.03.038>

Hahn, R. A., & Truman, B. I. (2015). Education improves public health equity. *International Journal of Health Services Planning, Administration, Evaluation*, 45(4), 657–678.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0020731415585986>

Hammer, E. S., & Cipolla, M. J. (2015). Cerebrovascular dysfunction in preeclamptic pregnancies. *Current Hypertension Reports*, 17(8). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11906-015-0575-8>

Hao, J., Hassen, D., Hao, Q., Graham, J., Paglia, M. J., Brown, J., Cooper, M., Schlieder, V., & Snyder, S. R. (2019). Maternal and infant health care costs related to preeclampsia. *Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 134(6), 1227–1233.

<https://doi.org/10.97/aog.0000000000003581>

Haxton, D., Doering, J., Gingras, L., & Kelly, L. (2012). Implementing skin-to-skin contact at birth using the Iowa model. *Nursing for Women's Health*, 16(3), 222–230.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11906-020-01058-w>

HealthStream. (2021, April 1.). *Gaging the readiness of new perinatal safety standards of nurses: HealthStream.*

<https://www.healthstream.com/resources/blog/blog/2020/08/14/surveyed-healthcare-organizations-reveal-their-readiness-for-the-joint-commission-s-new-standards-for-perinatal-safety>.

Healy, S. J., Black, D., Harris, C., Lorenz, A., & Dungan, K. M. (2013). Inpatient diabetes education is associated with less frequent hospital readmission among patients with poor glycemic control. *Diabetes Care*, 36(10), 2960–2967. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc13-0108>

- Hirshberg, A., Levine, L. D., & Srinivas, S. K. (2016). Clinical factors associated with readmission for postpartum hypertension in women with pregnancy-related hypertension: A nested case-control study. *Journal of Perinatology*, *36*(5), 405–409.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/jp.2015.209>
- Howard-Anderson, J., Busuttill, A., Lonowski, S., Vangala, S., & Afsar-manesh, N. (2016). From discharge to readmission: Understanding the process from the patient perspective. *Journal of Hospital Medicine*, *11*(6), 407–412. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jhm.2560>
- Iowa Model Collaborative, Buckwalter, K. C., Cullen, L., Hanrahan, K., Kleiber, C., McCarthy, A. M., Rakel, B., Steelman, V., Tripp-Reimer, T., & Tucker, S. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, *14*(3), 175-182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12223>
- The Joint Commission. (2019). *Provision of care, treatment, and service standards for maternal safety*. https://www.jointcommission.org/-/media/tjc/documents/standards/r3-reports/r3_24_maternal_safety_hap_9_6_19_final1.pdf
- Johnson, P. D., Duzyj, C. M., Howell, E. A., & Janevic, T. (2019). Patient and hospital characteristics associated with severe maternal morbidity among postpartum readmissions. *Journal of Perinatology*, *39*(9), 1204–1212.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41372-019-0426-6>
- Kaiser Permanente. (2019, August 5). *Health care services*.
<https://healthy.kaiserpermanente.org/health-wellness/maternity>
- Katsi, V., Skalis, G., Vamvakou, G., Tousouslis, D., & Makris, T. (2020). Postpartum hypertension. *Current Hypertension Reports*, *22*(8), 58–58.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11906-020-01058-w>

- Knapp, T.R. (2016). Why is the one-group pretest-posttest design still used? *Clinical Nursing Research, 25*(5), 467–472. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1054773816666280>
- Lacerenza, C. N., Marlow, S. L., Tannenbaum, S. I., & Salas, E. (2018). Team development interventions: Evidence-based approaches for improving teamwork. *American Psychologist, 73*(4), 517–531. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000295>
- Langer, A., Villar, J., Tell, K., Kim, T., & Kennedy, S. (2008). Reducing eclampsia-related deaths—a call to action. *Lancet, 371*(9614), 705-706. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(08\)60321-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(08)60321-9)
- Langley, G.J., Moen, R. D., Nolan, K. M., Nolan, T. W., Norman, C. L., & Provost, L. P. (2009). *The improvement guide: A practical approach to enhancing organizational performance* (2nd ed). Jossey Bass.
- LeFevre, M. L. (2014). Low-dose aspirin use for the prevention of morbidity and mortality from preeclampsia: U.S. preventive services task force recommendation statement. *Annals of Internal Medicine, 161*(11), 819. <https://doi.org/10.7326/m14-1884>
- Levine, L. D., Nkonde-Price, C., Limaye, M., & Srinivas, S. K. (2016). Factors associated with postpartum follow-up and persistent hypertension among women with severe preeclampsia. *Journal of Perinatology, 36*(12), 1079–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1038/jp.2016.137>
- Lewis, N. L. (2020). Developing a hospital-based postpartum depression education intervention for perinatal nurses. *Journal for Nurses in Professional Development, 36*(1), 7–11. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NND.0000000000000595>
- Lowdermilk, D. L., Perry, S. E., Cashion, M. C., & Alden, K. R. (2015). *Maternity and women's & health care*. Mosby.

Lindpaintner, L. S., Gasser, J. T., Schramm, M. S., Cina-Tschumi, B., Müller, B., & Beer, J. H. (2013). Discharge intervention pilot improves satisfaction for patients and professionals. *European Journal of Internal Medicine*, *24*(8), 756–762.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejim.2013.08.703>

Logsdon, M. C., Davis, D. W., Myers, J. A., Masterson, K. M., Rushton, J. A., & Lauf, A. P. (2018). Do new mothers understand the risk factors for maternal mortality? *American Journal of Maternal/Child Nursing*, *43*(4), 201–205.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/nmc.0000000000000434>

Lopes Perdigao, J., Hirshberg, A., Koelper, N., Srinivas, S. K., Sammel, M. D., & Levine, L. D. (2020). Postpartum blood pressure trends are impacted by race and BMI. *Pregnancy Hypertension*, *20*, 14–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preghy.2020.02.006>

Mahajan, A., Kemp, A., Hawkins, T. L.-A., Metcalfe, A., Dowling, S., & Nerenberg, K. (2020). Postpartum hypertensive disorders in the emergency department – A retrospective review of local practice in Calgary, Alberta. *Pregnancy Hypertension*, *19*, 212–217.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preghy.2019.11.009>

Main, E. K., McCain, C. L., Morton, C. H., Holtby, S., & Lawton, E. S. (2015). Pregnancy-related mortality in California. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, *125*(4), 938–947.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/aog.0000000000000746>

Malagon-Maldonado, G., Connelly, C. D., & Bush, R. A. (2017). Predictors of readiness for hospital discharge after birth: Building evidence for practice. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, *14*(2), 118–127. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12208>

Maric-Bilkan, C., Abrahams, V. M., Arteaga, S. S., Bourjeily, G., Conrad, K. P., Catov, J. M., Costantine, M. M., Cox, B., Garovic, V., George, E. M., Gernard, A. D., Jeyabalan, A.,

- Karumanchi, S. A., Laposky, A. D., Miodovnik, M., Mitchell, M., Pemberton, V. L., Reddy, U. M., Santillan, ... Roberts, J. M. (2019). Research recommendations from the national institutes of health workshop on predicting, preventing, and treating preeclampsia. *Hypertension*, *73*(4), 757–766.
<https://doi.org/10.1161/hypertensionaha.118.11644>
- Marsden, E., & Torgerson, C. J. (2012). Single group, pre- and post-test research designs: Some methodological concerns. *Oxford Review of Education*, *38*(5), 583–616.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2012.731208>
- Matei, A., Saccone, G., Vogel, J. P., & Armson, A. B. (2019). Primary and secondary prevention of preterm birth: a review of systematic reviews and ongoing randomized controlled trials. *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, *236*, 224–239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2018.12.022>
- McCarter-Spaulding, D., & Shea, S. (2016). Effectiveness of discharge education on postpartum depression. *American Journal of Maternal/Child Nursing*, *41*(3), 168–172.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/nmc.0000000000000236>
- Miller, S., Lattanzio, M., & Cohen, S. (2016). “Teach-back” from a patient’s perspective. *Nursing*, *46*(2), 63–64. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.nurse.0000476249.18503.f5>
- Mogos, M. F., Salemi, J. L., Spooner, K. K., McFarlin, B. L., & Salihu, H. H. (2018). Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and postpartum readmission in the United States. *Journal of Hypertension*, *36*(3), 608–618. <https://doi.org/10.1097/hjh.0000000000001594>
- Morley, C.M., & Levin, S. A. (2021). Health literacy, health confidence, and simulation: A novel approach to patient education to reduce readmissions. *Professional Case Management*, *26*(3), 138–149. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NCM.0000000000000456>

- Morton, C. H., VanOtterloo, L. R., Seacrist, M. J., & Main, E. K. (2019). Translating maternal mortality review into quality improvement opportunities in response to pregnancy-related deaths in California. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 48(3), 252–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2019.03.003>
- O’Leary, J., Nash, R., & Lewis, P. (2016). Standard instruction versus simulation: educating registered nurses in the early recognition of patient deterioration in pediatric critical care. *Nurse Education Today*, 36, 287–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2015.07.021>
- O’Meara, S., & Lepic, M. (2016). What clinical interventions have been implemented to prevent or reduce postpartum hypertension readmissions? *A Clin-IQ. Journal of Patient-Centered Research and Reviews*, 3(3), 150–152. <https://doi.org/10.17294/2330-0698.1264>
- Peneva, D., Xu, X., Sutton, A., Triche, E., Ehrenkranz, R., Paidas, M., Stevens, W., & Shih, T. (2016). The rising burden of preeclampsia in the United States impacts both maternal and child health. *American Journal of Perinatology*, 33(04), 329–338. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0035-1564881>
- Perdigao, J. L., Hirshberg, A., Koelper, N., Srinivas, S. K., Sammel, M. D., & Levine, L. D. (2020). Postpartum blood pressure trends are impacted by race and BMI. *Pregnancy Hypertension*, 20, 14–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preghy.2020.02.006>
- Phillips, C., & Boyd, M. (2016). Assessment, management, and health implications of early-onset preeclampsia. *Nursing for Women’s Health*, 20(4), 400–414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nwh.2016.07.003>
- Phipps, E., Prasanna, D., Brima, W., & Jim, B. (2016). Preeclampsia: updates in pathogenesis, definitions, and guidelines. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*, 11(6), 1102–1113. <https://doi.org/10.2215/cjn.12081115>

- Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2017). *Nursing research: generating and assessing evidence for nursing practice*. Wolters Kluwer/Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.
- Polster, D. (2015). Preventing readmissions with discharge education. *Nursing Management*, 46(10), 30–37. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.NUMA.0000471590.62056.77>
- Powles, K., & Gandhi, S. (2017). Postpartum hypertension. *Canadian Medical Association Journal*, 189(27), E913. <https://doi.org/10.1503/cmaj.160785>
- Preeclampsia Foundation. (2020, March 17). *Postpartum preeclampsia: Moms are still at risk after delivery*. <https://www.preeclampsia.org/current-guidelines>
- Provost, L. P., & Murray, S. K. (2011). *The health care data guide: learning from data for improvement*. Jossey-Bass.
- Redman, E., Hauspurg, A., Hubel, C., Roberts, J., & Jeyabalan, A. (2019). Clinical course, associated factors, and blood pressure profile of delayed-onset postpartum preeclampsia. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 134(5), 995–1001. <https://doi.org/10.1097/aog.0000000000003508>
- Reid, C., Jones, L., Hurst, C., & Anderson, D. (2018). Examining relationships between socio-demographics and self-efficacy among registered nurses in Australia. *Collegian*, 25(1), 57–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colegn.2017.03.007>
- Ross, G. M. (2019). What is eclampsia? <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/253960-overview#a1>
- Sharma, K. J., & Kilpatrick, S. J. (2017). Postpartum hypertension. *Obstetrical & Gynecological Survey*, 72(4), 248–252. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ogx.0000000000000424>
- Skurnik, G., Hurwitz, S., McElrath, T. F., Tsen, L. C., Duey, S., Saxena, A. R., Karumanchi, A., Rich-Edwards, J. W., & Seely, E. W. (2017). Labor therapeutics and BMI as risk factors

- for postpartum preeclampsia: A case-control study. *Pregnancy Hypertension*, 10, 177–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preghy.2017.07.142>
- Spurlock, D. R. (2018). The single-group, pre- and posttest design in nursing education: It's time to move on. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 57(2), 69–71. <https://doi.org/10.3928/01484834-20180123-02>
- Suplee, P. D., Bingham, D., & Kleppel, L. (2017). Nurses' knowledge and teaching of possible postpartum complications. *American Journal of Maternal/Child Nursing*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1097/nmc.0000000000000371>
- Suplee, P. D., Kleppel, L., & Bingham, D. (2016a). Discharge education on maternal morbidity and mortality provided by nurses to women in the postpartum period. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 45(6), 894–904. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2016.07.006>
- Suplee, P. D., Kleppel, L., Santa-Donato, A., & Bingham, D. (2016b). Improving postpartum education about warning signs of maternal morbidity and mortality. *Nursing for Women's Health*, 20(6), 552–567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nwh.2016.10.009>
- Sutton, A. L. M., Harper, L. M., & Tita, A. T. N. (2018). Hypertensive disorders in pregnancy. *Obstetrics and Gynecology Clinics of North America*, 45(2), 333–347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ogc.2018.01.012>
- Takaoka, S., Ishii, K., Taguchi, T., Kakubari, R., Muto, H., & Mabuchi, A., Yamamoto, R., Hayashi, S., & Mitsuda, N. (2016). Clinical features and antenatal risk factors for postpartum-onset hypertensive disorders. *Hypertension In Pregnancy*, 35(1), 22–31. <https://doi.org/10.3109/10641955.2015.1100308>

- Tedesco, E. R., Whiteman, K., Heuston, M., Swanson-Biearman, B., & Stephens, K. (2017). Interprofessional collaboration to improve sepsis care and survival within a tertiary care emergency department. *Journal of Emergency Nursing*, *43*(6), 532–538.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jen.2017.04.014>
- Temiz, Z., Ozturk, D., Ugras, G. A., Oztekin, S. D., & Sengul, E. (2016). Determination of patient learning needs after thyroidectomy. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention*, *17*(3), 1479–1483. <https://doi.org/10.7314/apjcp.2016.17.3.1479>
- Titler, M. G., Kleiber, C., Steelman, V., Goode, C., Rakel, B., Barry-Walker, J., Small, S., & Buckwalter, K. (1994). Infusing research into practice to promote quality care. *Nursing Research*, *43*(5), 307–313. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00006199-199409000-00009>
- Titler, M.G., Kleiber, C., Steelman, V.J., Rakel, B.A., Budreau, G., Everett, L.Q., Buckwalter, K.C., Tripp-Reimer, T., & Goode, C.J. (2001). The Iowa model of evidence-based practice to promote quality care. *Critical Care Nursing Clinics of North America*, *13*(4), 497-509.
- Townsend, R., O'Brien, P., & Khalil, A. (2016). Current best practice in the management of hypertensive disorders in pregnancy. *Integrated Blood Pressure Control*, *9*, 79–94.
<https://doi.org/10.2147/ibpc.s77344>
- Tran, S., Fogel, J., Karrar, S., & Hong, P. (2020). Comparison of process outcomes, clinical symptoms and laboratory values between patients with antepartum preeclampsia, antepartum with persistent postpartum preeclampsia, and new onset postpartum preeclampsia. *Journal of Gynecology Obstetrics and Human Reproduction*, *49*(5), 101724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogoh.2020.101724>
- Troiano, N. H., & Witcher, P. M. (2018). Maternal mortality and morbidity in the United States.

Journal of Perinatal & Neonatal Nursing, 32(3), 222–231.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/jpn.0000000000000349>

Tucker, S. J., Olson, M. E., & Frusti, D. K. (2009). Evidence-based practice self-efficacy scale.

Clinical Nurse Specialist, 23(4), 207–215. <https://doi.org/10.1097/nur.0b013e3181aae8c6>

Van Houwelingen, T., Ettema, R. G. A., Bleijenberg, N., van Os-Medendorp, H., Kort, H. S. M.,

& ten Cate, O. (2021). Educational intervention to increase nurses' knowledge, self-efficacy and usage of telehealth: A multi-setting pretest-posttest study. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 51, 102924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102924>

Vigil-De Gracia, P. (2009). Maternal deaths due to eclampsia and HELLP syndrome.

International Journal of Gynaecology and Obstetrics, 104(2), 90-94.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgo.2008.09.014>

Vilchez, G., Hoyos, L. R., Leon-Peters, J., Lagos, M., & Argoti, P. (2016). Differences in

clinical presentation and pregnancy outcomes in antepartum preeclampsia and new-onset postpartum preeclampsia: Are these the same disorder? *Obstetrics & Gynecology Science*, 59(6), 434. <https://doi.org/10.5468/ogs.2016.59.6.434>

Wadhwa, R., & Huynh, A. P. (2020, April 30). *The Joint Commission. StatPearls*.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK557846/>.

Wagner, J. L., White, R. S., Tangel, V., Gupta, S., & Pick, J. S. (2019). Socioeconomic, racial, and ethnic disparities in postpartum readmissions in patients with preeclampsia: A multi-

state analysis, 2007–2014. *Journal of Racial and Ethnic Health Disparities*, 6(4), 806–820. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40615-019-00580-1>

Warde, F., Papadakos, J., Papadakos, T., Rodin, D., Salhia, M., & Giuliani, M. (2018). Plain language communication as a priority competency for medical professionals in a

globalized world. *Canadian Medical Education Journal*, 9(2), e52–59.

<https://doi.org/10.36834/cmej.36848>

Weiss, M. E., & Lokken, L. (2009). Predictors and outcomes of postpartum mothers' perceptions of readiness for discharge after birth. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 38(4), 406–417. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.2009.01040.x>

Wen, T., Krenitsky, N. M., Clapp, M. A., D'Alton, M. E., Wright, J. D., Attenello, F., Mack, W. J., & Friedman, A. M. (2020). Fragmentation of postpartum readmissions in the United States. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 223(2), 252.e1–252.e14.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2020.01.022>

Wen, T., Wright, J. D., Goffman, D., D'Alton, M. E., Attenello, F. J., Mack, W. J., & Friedman, A. M. (2019). Hypertensive postpartum admissions among women without a history of hypertension or preeclampsia. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 133(4), 712–719.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/aog.0000000000003099>

World Health Organization, Who recommendations on drug treatment for non-severe hypertension in pregnancy (2018).

Yen, P. H., & Leasure, A. R. (2019). Use and effectiveness of the teach-back method in patient education and health outcomes. *Federal Practitioner*, 36(6), 284–289.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6590951/>

Ziadi, M., Héon, M., Aita, M., & Charbonneau, L. (2016). A pilot nursing educational intervention promoting an evidence-based transition from gavage to direct breastfeeding in a NICU. *Journal of Neonatal Nursing*, 22(3), 124–137.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnn.2015.07.010>

Zuckerwise, L.C., & Lipkind, H.S. (2017). Maternal early warning systems-Towards reducing preventable maternal mortality and severe maternal morbidity through improved clinical surveillance and responsiveness. *Seminars In Perinatology*, *41*(3), 161–165.

<https://doi.org/10.1053/j.semperi.2017.03.005>

APPENDIX A**Approval Notice**

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects
P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719
/ F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton

February 28, 2021

From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board

To: PI: Beleda Saziru

Application No. HSR-20-21-300

Study Title: Utilizing the Joint Commission Perinatal Standards in the Development of a Nursing Education Program

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(ii). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording).

Any disclosure of the human subjects' responses outside the research would not reasonably place the subjects at risk of criminal or civil liability or be damaging to the subjects' financial standing, employability, educational advancement, or reputation.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposed was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation. Additionally, the principal

investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office
Manal Alatrash

APPENDIX B**Postpartum Knowledge and Teaching Survey**

Demographics Survey

1. What is your age:
 - a. 20-30
 - b. 31-40
 - c. 41-50
 - d. 51-60
 - e. >61

2. What is your highest level of nursing education completed?
 - a. Diploma
 - b. Associate degree
 - c. Baccalaureate degree
 - d. Master's degree
 - e. DNP
 - f. PhD
 - g. Other

3. If you hold a certain certification which specialty are you certified in?
 - a. RNC-MNN
 - b. RNC-OB
 - c. CLEC
 - d. IBCLC
 - e. Other
 - f. None of the above

4. How many years have you been practicing postpartum nursing?
 - a. Less than one year
 - b. 1-2 years
 - c. 3-5 years
 - d. 6-10 years
 - e. 11-20 years
 - f. Greater than 20 years

5. In which state are you employed:

6. Are you aware of the two new JC standards?
 - a. No
 - b. Yes

7. What are the new standards?
 - a. Postpartum Infection
 - b. Postpartum Hemorrhage
 - c. Infection Sepsis
 - d. Postpartum Hypertension/Preeclampsia

8. How many births does your hospital report a year?
 - a.<1000
 - b.1001-3000
 - c.3001-5000
 - d.>5001
 - e. Not sure

9. What is your total cesarean rate per year?
 - a. <20%
 - b. 21-30%
 - c. 31-40%
 - d. 41-50%
 - e. >51%
 - f. Not sure

MATERNAL MORBIDITY & MORTALITY KNOWLEDGE

10. Approximately how many women in the U.S. die each year from pregnancy related complications?
 - a. 250 per year (6 per 100,000 births)
 - b. 350 per year (9 per 100,000 births)
 - c. 500 per year (15.5 per 100,000 births)
 - d. 600 per year (16.0 per 100,000 births)
 - e. 700 per year (17.3 per 100,000 births)
 - f. 800 per year (20 per 100,000 births)
 - g. 1000 per year (25 per 100,000 births)

11. What percentage of the total number of maternal deaths takes place in the postpartum period?
 - a. 12
 - b. 23
 - c. 34
 - d. 45
 - e. 52
 - f. 75
 - g. 80

12. Please rank the top three leading causes of maternal mortality in the U.S.
- Amniotic fluid embolism
 - Anesthesia complications
 - Cardiovascular diseases
 - Cerebrovascular accidents
 - Diabetes
 - Hemorrhage
 - Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy
 - Infection or sepsis
 - Postpartum depression
 - Thrombotic pulmonary embolism
 - Other: _____
13. In the last decade, maternal morbidity has:
- Decreased
 - Stayed the same
 - Increased

MATERNITY MORBIDITY & MORTALITY TEACHING

14. When do nurses on your unit provide the **MAJORITY** of postpartum discharge education to women?
- On the first day of admission to the postpartum unit
 - Throughout the hospital stay
 - On the day of discharge from the hospital
15. On the day of discharge, specifically, how much time does a nurse spend reinforcing **ALL** postpartum discharge information with women?
- Less than 10 min
 - 11-20 min
 - 21-30 min
 - 31-40 min
 - 41-50 min
 - Greater than 50 min
 - Add comment box
16. Please respond to the following statement: It is the postpartum nurse's responsibility to teach warning signs of potential complications of pregnancy to **ALL** women prior to discharge even if they do not have risk factors or identified complications?
- Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
 - Add comment box

17. On average, how much time does a nurse spend teaching about **warning signs of potential complications of pregnancy** with women prior to them being discharged from the hospital?

- f. Less than 5 min
- g. 6-10 min
- h. 11-15 min
- i. 16-20 min
- j. 21-30 min
- k. Greater than 30 min

18. How likely are you to discuss the following topics related to complications of pregnancy with ALL women prior to their discharge from the postpartum unit?

	Very Likely	Likely	Somewhat Likely	Not Likely	I only discuss if the woman has a relevant medical condition or history
Hemorrhage					
Hypertension					
Infection					
Venous Thrombosis					
Pulmonary Embolism					
Postpartum Depression					
Preeclampsia Eclampsia					

Cardiac Event					
---------------	--	--	--	--	--

19. How likely are you to discuss the following potential signs and symptoms of complications with ALL postpartum women prior to discharge?

	Very Likely	Likely	Somewhat Likely	Not Likely	I only discuss if the woman has a relevant medical condition or history
Severe, constant Headache					
Vision Changes					
Swelling of hands and feet					
Weight gain					
Elevated Blood Pressure					
Seizures					
Difficulty breathing or Shortness of Breath					
Chest Pain					
Thoughts of hurting baby or self					
Feeling depressed					
Bleeding – saturating one or more peri pads per hour					
Passing clots larger than egg					
Nausea, dizziness					

Swelling of one leg					
Redness or warmth of calf area					
Pain in calf area					
Temperature greater than 100.4F (38 Celsius)					
Bad smelling discharge					

20. How competent do you feel discussing the following topics with **ALL** women prior to discharge?

	Very Competent	Competent	Somewhat Competent	Not Competent	Don't feel it necessary
Hemorrhage					
Hypertension					
Infection					
Deep Vein Thrombosis					
Pulmonary Embolism					
Postpartum Depression					
Preeclampsia/Eclampsia					
Cardiac Event					

21. How helpful would it be to have a one-page educational handout to reinforce key concepts when talking to postpartum women about warning signs and when to obtain medical care?

- a. Very helpful
- b. Helpful
- c. Somewhat helpful
- d. Not helpful

22. How do you document that the postpartum education was completed in your institution?

- e. Written checklist
- f. Computerized checklist
- g. Combination of both
- h. Other

23. How likely would you use the following resources to increase your knowledge about postpartum morbidity and mortality?

	Very Likely	Likely	Somewhat Likely	Not Likely
Online education				
Written Article				
In-person workshop				
Conference				

Other: _____

24. How do you stay current with evidence-based practice in maternal/infant?

- a. Read journals, books or published guidelines
- b. Discussions with other nurses
- c. Attend conferences or in-person events
- d. Participate in online courses

25. Do you think there is a relationship between postpartum education that you provide women prior to them being discharged from the hospital and postpartum maternal mortality and morbidity?

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Explain answer here:

APPENDIX C

Self-Efficacy Scale

PICK ONE OF THESE NUMBERS AND WRITE ON THE LINE NEXT TO EACH ITEM BELOW.

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Not confident

Moderately Confident

Confident

I am THIS PERCENT confident I can complete the following activities that support nursing practice:

1. Routinely ask questions about my practice. _____%
2. Locate resources in my department and institution to facilitate my understanding of research literature relevant to my nursing practice. _____%
3. Locate resources in my department and institution necessary to institute an evidence-based change. _____%
4. Locate and review published practice guidelines that support nursing interventions important to my practice. _____%
5. Locate and review published research studies that have relevance to nursing interventions important to my practice _____%
6. Organize the necessary support and procedures to make a nursing practice changed based on evidence (research, clinical practice guidelines, clinical expertise, patient goals/preferences)_____%
7. Routinely identify patient outcomes to target nursing interventions _____%

8. Integrate the various sources of evidence and apply to my specialty population and practice _____%
9. Activate the processes to implement an evidence-based practice change _____%
10. Modify nursing interventions recommended for my patient population based on characteristics of the specific unit in which I work. _____%
11. Routinely evaluate the research literature and other sources of evidence related to nursing interventions for my specialty population and practice _____%
12. Routinely implement nursing interventions that are supported by evidence (research and other sources such as practice guidelines) for my patient population and practice. _____%
13. Modify nursing interventions I routinely implement based on what I learn about my patient's preferences. _____%
14. Routinely modify nursing interventions based on outcomes and goals _____%
15. Routinely evaluate the effectiveness of nursing interventions using measurable outcomes. _____%
16. Obtain proper training and education to be able to effectively implement an evidence-based nursing intervention or practice. _____%
17. Implement an evidence-based nursing intervention individualized to my patient/family situation without losing the fidelity of the intervention (i.e., delivering as it was intended to be delivered). _____

APPENDIX D

Educational Pamphlet

You are **STILL AT RISK** **after** your baby is born!

Postpartum Preeclampsia

What is it?

Postpartum preeclampsia is a serious disease related to high blood pressure. It can happen to any woman who has just had a baby **up to 6 weeks after the baby is born.**

Risks to You

- Seizures
- Stroke
- Organ damage
- Death

Warning Signs

- | | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---|--|
| | Severe headaches |
| | Seeing spots (or other vision changes) |
| | Shortness of breath |

What can you do?

- Ask if you should follow up with your doctor within one week of discharge.
- Keep all follow-up appointments.
- Watch for warning signs. If you notice any, call your doctor. (If you can't reach your doctor, call 911 or go directly to an emergency room and report you have been pregnant.)
- Trust your instincts.

For more information, go to www.stillatrisk.org

Copyright © 2018 Preeclampsia Foundation. All Rights Reserved.

Note. Permission obtained from the PreeclampsiaFoundation.org

APPENDIX E

Permission Letter to Use Iowa Model

Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics <survey-bounce@survey.uiowa.edu
>
Sat 11/14/2020 7:21 PM

You have permission, as requested today, to review and/or reproduce *The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care*. Click the link below to open.

[The Iowa Model Revised \(2015\)](#)

Copyright is retained by University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics. **Permission is not granted for placing on the Internet.**

Citation: Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182. doi:10.1111/wvn.12223

In written material, please add the following statement:

Used/reprinted with permission from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics, copyright 2015. For permission to use or reproduce, please contact the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics at 319-384-9098.

Please contact UIHCNursingResearchandEBP@uiowa.edu or 319-384-9098 with questions.

APPENDIX F

Research Study Consent Form

California State University, Fullerton

Study Title: Utilizing the Joint Commission Perinatal Standard in the Development of a Nurse Education Program on Postpartum Hypertension and Preeclampsia

Protocol Number:

Researchers: Beleda Saziru, MSN, RNC-MNN, CLEC
Manal Alatrash, PhD, RN

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by Beleda Saziru, a Doctor of Nursing Practice student and Manal Alatrash, a Professor in the School of Nursing at California State University, Fullerton. This consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the project. Please read this form carefully and feel free to ask the principal investigator if you have any questions about the project. You can decide not to participate in the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

This is a quality improvement project to reduce complications related to postpartum hypertension and preeclampsia, consequently reducing related readmissions to the hospital. The Joint Commission (JC) issued a new perinatal standard that is mandated to start on January 1, 2021. The new standard focuses on maternal postpartum hypertension and preeclampsia. This study will examine changes in postpartum nurses' knowledge about postpartum hypertension and preeclampsia and in their self-efficacy related to educating patients about postpartum hypertension and preeclampsia after the completion of an educational session.

The educational session will discuss the definition of the disorder, postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia, signs and symptoms, risk factors, and specific patient education areas that perinatal nurses should teach their patients about to prevent complications of this disorder and subsequent readmissions.

To take part in this project, you must be at least 18 years old, a registered nurse, and work primarily in the postpartum unit.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

You will be asked to complete the project survey to assess your demographic characteristics, your knowledge of postpartum complications and about your self-efficacy to implement the new JC standard on the postpartum unit. You will complete this survey at baseline before conducting the education, which will take approximately 10-15 minutes. You will also be asked to attend an

educational session about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia of your choosing since this session will be offered five times on different days and shifts. Then you will be asked to complete the project survey another time after the completion of the educational session. No identifying information, such as your name, will be collected.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

The potential benefits to you for taking part in this project that you will help improve patient safety and quality of the care in postpartum patients. If you take part in this project, you may help reduce patient mortality and death in the future.

Are there any risks to me if I am in the study?

There are no identifiable risks in this study.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

Your information will be kept confidential. Neither the researcher nor anyone else will be able to link the information collected to you. No identifying information, such as your name, will be collected. You will be provided an unmarked envelope to place your completed survey, this envelope will be put in a pile with the other participants' envelopes and it will be numbered based on the order in which it will be received. The surveys will be kept in a locked cabinet in a locked private office. The information entered in the computer will be stored on a password protected laptop kept in the researcher's locked office. The results of this project will be reported collectively and cannot be linked to an individual participant.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study. You will receive a \$5 Starbucks™ gift card for to compensate you for your time.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have any questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the primary researcher Beleda Saziru: bsaziru1@csu.fullerton.edu. Mobile Phone: (818) 850-1671.

If you have questions about your rights as a research participant or would like to report a concern or issue about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719 or email irb@fullerton.edu.

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or questions that make you uncomfortable or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
 - You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
 - The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
 - You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.
-

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or I agree to the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You will be given a copy of this signed and dated consent form to keep.

Name of Participant (please print) _____

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

Your signature below indicates that you are giving permission to audio/video tape your responses.

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

APPENDIX G

Permission to Use Self Efficacy Scale

From: Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics <survey-bounce@survey.uiowa.edu>
Sent: Saturday, November 14, 2020 7:21 PM
To: Saziru, Beleda<bsaziru1@csu.fullerton.edu>
Subject: Permission to Use Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self-Efficacy Scale

California State University - Fullerton

Thank you for your interest in the Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self-Efficacy Scale developed by Sharon Tucker, PhD, RN; Marcelline Harris, PhD, RN; and Mariann E. Olson, PhD, RN. This tool may be useful for assessing nurses' confidence with EBP skills. Permission is granted as requested today, it is not granted for revising or modifying.

Following is a link to the scale and instructions for use. Cronbach coefficients ranged from .95 to .98. Average scores increased significantly ($p < .01$) following an evidence-based practice educational program. We ask that you share what you learned and submit your data for us to complete further psychometric evaluation. You are responsible for data management and analysis for use within your organization. Please format as an Excel file as follows with the questions across the top and the respondent number in the left column:

Respondent ID	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Etc through Q 17	Comments
1									
2 (etc)									

The number of the answer circled (or the comment) goes in the appropriate cell. Please email the Excel file to laura-cullen@uiowa.edu.

Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self Efficacy Scale

Citation:

Tucker, S. J., Olson, M. E. & Frusti, D. K. (2009). Evidence-based practice self-efficacy scale: Preliminary reliability and validity. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 23(4), 207-215.
doi:10.1097/NUR.0b013e3181aae8c6

Thank you for your interest. We are excited for the nursing community to use this scale. If you have any questions, please contact Laura Cullen at 319-384-9144 or laura-cullen@uiowa.edu.

APPENDIX H

Permission to use Postpartum Nursing Knowledge Teaching Survey

Trish Suplee <trishsuplee@gmail.com>

Tue 11/10/2020 9:59 AM

To: Saziru, Beleda; Debra Bingham <dbingham@perinatalqi.org>

Hi Beleda:

You are welcome to use our survey which is attached. Please note that it may need updating as we developed it a few years ago. Best of luck with your work!

Trish

APPENDIX I**Permission to Use Postpartum Preeclampsia Pamphlet**

Rebecca Britt <rebecca.britt@preeclampsia.org>
To: bsaziru@yahoo.com
Cc: Jennifer Sea

Beleda,
Feel free to use our tear pad, as long as you make reference to the Preeclampsia Foundation.

Thank you.

Rebecca Britt
Director of Education & Engagement
Preeclampsia Foundation
3840 EauGallie Blvd. Suite 104
Melbourne, FL 32934 USA
321.421.6957 (office)
www.preeclampsia.org

-
-
-
-

Appendix J

Recruitment Flyer

**** ATTENTION POSTPARTUM REGISTERED NURSES ****

LOOKING FOR VOLUNTEERS!

WHAT DO YOU KNOW ABOUT POSTPARTUM HYPERTENSION PREECLAMPSIA?

In recent years, hospital readmissions for postpartum hypertension and preeclampsia have increased. The new Joint Commission perinatal standards were developed to reduce the maternal morbidity and mortality associated with this diagnosis.

I am conducting a quality improvement project to educate postpartum nurses about postpartum hypertension and preeclampsia to prevent related complications after discharge. The project will assess the nurses' self-efficacy in using the new Joint Commission perinatal standard and will examine their knowledge of postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia.

HOW YOU CAN HELP

Please contact the principal investigator Beleda Saziru if you meet eligibility criteria & would like to volunteer to participate in the project.

Participants will receive a \$5-gift card in compensation for their time. Your participation is valued & appreciated. Thank you!

FOR MORE INFORMATION CALL
(818) 850-1671
 Beleda Saziru
bsaziru1@nsu.fullerton.edu

TO BE ELIGIBLE PARTICIPANTS MUST BE:

1. OVER 18 YEARS-OLD
2. A REGISTERED NURSE
3. WORK IN THE POSTPARTUM UNIT

Made with PosterMyWall.com

Appendix K

IRB Approval

KAISER PERMANENTE®

Southern California Permanente Medical Group

California State University Fullerton (CSUF) Institutional Review Board (IRB)
Titan Hall-ASC 228
800 N. State College Blvd.
Fullerton, CA 92832

February 14, 2021

Dear CSUF IRB,

Based on my review of the proposed DNP project by Beleda Saziru, I give permission for her to conduct the project entitled "Utilizing the Joint Commission Perinatal Standard in Development of a Nurse Education Program Regarding Postpartum Hypertension and Preeclampsia" within the Postpartum Department of Kaiser Permanente Los Angeles Medical Center (LAMC) at 4867 Sunset Blvd, Los Angeles, CA 90027. As part of this study, I authorize the student to conduct an anonymous survey, review readmission rates, analyze and disseminate survey data, and create an educational intervention based upon the collected data and literature review. Individuals' participation will be voluntary and at their own discretion.

We understand that our organization's responsibilities include access to patient information and assistance with creating and disseminating the educational intervention in conjunction with the Department of Education. We reserve the right to withdraw from the project at any time if our circumstances change.

We understand that the research will include two brief anonymous paper-and-pen surveys and a follow-up educational intervention.

This authorization covers the time period of February 2021-May 2021.

I confirm that I am authorized to approve research in this setting.

I understand that data collected will remain entirely confidential and may not be provided to anyone outside of the research team without permission from the California State University Fullerton IRB.

Sincerely,

Tanisha Dickens, MSN
Director of Maternal Child Health